

PILOTING AND VALIDATING INTERVENTION ASSESSMENTS

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Please cite this report as:

Azadi, T., d’Haenens, L., De Nolf, A., Ponte, C., Luna, E., Tomczyk, Ł., Donoso, V., Torres da Silva, M., Batista, S., & Żegleń, M.(2025). *Piloting And Validating Tailored Pre- and Post-Intervention Assessments for PRODIGI Target Groups*. PRODIGI, KU Leuven.

Disclaimer

PRODIGI is funded by the European Union, under Grant Agreement no. 101182849. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them.

PILOTING AND VALIDATING TAILORED PRE- AND POST-INTERVENTION ASSESSMENTS FOR PRODIGI TARGET GROUPS

Work package 1 – Deliverable D1.2

Submission date: 19 December 2025

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1. Executive Summary

PRODIGI adopts pre- and post-test designs, using the Youth AI Literacy Scale (yAILS) and the Senior AI Literacy Scale (sAILS), to assess AI literacy and digital skills. Both the Youth AI Literacy Scale and the Senior AI Literacy Scale are newly developed within the PRODIGI project to ensure age-appropriate measurement and contextual relevance.

In this report we document and report the development, piloting, and initial validation of PRODIGI's pre- and post-intervention assessment tool for measuring AI literacy, among vulnerable populations in Belgium, Portugal, and Poland. This assessment tool forms the empirical backbone for evaluating upcoming intervention programmes in PRODIGI's Work Package 2.

First, we began with a rapid review of existing digital-skills and AI-literacy assessments. The review showed that many existing tools:

- *focus on self-perceived knowledge* instead of demonstrated skills,
- *rarely address the needs of vulnerable groups,*
- *do not include emerging competencies around AI systems,* such as understanding algorithms, identifying bias, or reasoning about ethical implications.

In response, PRODIGI built upon the Youth Digital Skills Indicator (yDSI).¹ as the conceptual framework and developed a new scale covering the four underlying digital skill dimensions of yDSI as well as a fifth domain: ethics & responsible AI use, *extending the framework to capture contemporary AI-mediated challenges*. Our instrument, hereafter referred to as the AI Literacy Scale, was translated into partner languages and tested by structured expert consultations and cognitive interviews with target groups to ensure comprehensibility, cultural fit, and age appropriateness. Moreover, a large-scale pilot (among 1,200 youngsters in Belgium) enabled exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to examine the instrument's structure.

Instead of the originally proposed five distinct conceptual domains, *the revised scale for youth is organised into four theoretically grounded and empirically coherent dimensions* that capture how young people understand and use AI in practice: *technical and operational, information navigation and processing, communication and content creation, and ethical and responsible use*.

These patterns reflect how *AI tasks require integrated, not isolated skills*: prompting, creating, evaluating, and ethical reasoning often co-occur. This supports a conceptual shift away from modular digital skills toward interwoven competencies shaped by human-AI interaction. This pilot identifies substantial *knowledge gaps in AI-usage*, as nearly half of the young participants achieved scores of 16 or fewer correct answers across 30 AI knowledge items. AI understanding varied strongly by educational track but not by gender.

Qualitative co-design research in Portugal, Poland, and Belgium further shows that *youth, older people, and experts repeatedly requested the need for clearer, simplified language* and flagged scale items that felt too abstract, overly technical, or irrelevant to their lived experiences. This feedback was systematically integrated into substantial revisions of the scale items, enhancing clarity, age appropriateness, and contextual relevance across target groups.

¹ The yDSI (Youth Digital Skills Indicator) was developed under the H2020-ySKILLS (Youth SKILLS) project.

Key insights

From the rapid review:

The rapid review showed that several existing tools for assessing media, digital, and AI literacy are inadequate. Many rely on self-reported abilities rather than measuring what people can actually do, and they overlook skills that are increasingly important in an AI-driven world, such as understanding how AI works, recognising algorithmic influence, spotting biased or unfair information, or its societal and environmental impact. These tools were also not designed for or tested among vulnerable groups, including unaccompanied minors, disadvantaged youth, or older adults, who have varied levels of access and experience with technology. Given these gaps and the rapid pace of AI development, there is a clear *need for updated assessments that place a strong emphasis on ethics and the responsible use of AI while taking into account vulnerable and marginalised populations.*

From the experts:

The expert consultations helped improve relevance and clarity as well as the content and the wording of the assessment. *Experts recommended using simpler language and removing technical terms* that may be unfamiliar to many young people or in at-risk situations (e.g., due to a migration background). They also suggested adding clear examples, particularly for questions concerning responsibility, fairness, and other ethical issues, to help respondents relate these concepts to real-world situations. In addition, experts noted that some questions overlapped and encouraged a clearer separation among creative, ethical, communication, and information-checking skills. Overall, they stressed that *the assessment should be easy to understand across diverse cultural and linguistic contexts and should be developed in collaboration with the users* to ensure it remains clear and relevant.

From the cognitive interviews:

Across all three countries, our interviews indicated that participants across age groups are often curious about AI, yet struggle with the way current AI-related questions are formulated. *Many young people and seniors do not realise how much AI they already use in everyday apps*, find technical terms (such as “algorithm”, “bias”, “deepfake”) and long, abstract sentences complex to understand, and are confused by questions that do not match their real lives or skills.

The items that worked best were short, concrete, written in simple language, and tied to familiar activities such as using a chatbot for homework, writing birthday wishes, finding recipes, or checking whether a message looks suspicious. Overall, the key message is that, *to measure AI literacy fairly, we need fewer questions, more precise wording, everyday examples, and, at times, additional explanation or support.*

From the pilot study:

The pilot study with 1,200 young people helped test PRODIGI AI literacy scale for youth. The results showed that young people use AI-related skills in combination rather than as separate abilities. The first exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted on split sample 1 and yielded a four-factor solution. This solution was retained as the initial measurement model for the newly developed scale because it provided the clearest and most interpretable structure, with comparatively fewer problematic cross-loadings and less conceptual overlap between factors than alternative solutions. Items clustered into four meaningful components: Factor 1 (Content Creation and Communication),

Factor 2 (Ethics), Factor 3 (Information Navigation), and Factor 4 (Technical/Operational). This differs from earlier models and reflects how young people actually use AI. The study also found that many participants had limited knowledge about how AI functions. Nearly half answered 16 or fewer out of 30 questions correctly. Performance differences were primarily attributable to educational track, with academic students scoring higher than those in vocational programmes, whereas age and gender had little effect.

In conclusion

Developing this AI literacy scale requires several important considerations that emerged from our research with experts and with participants across Belgium, Portugal, and Poland.

1. First, the findings showed that *people do not think about AI skills in separate categories*. Instead, skills such as content creation, communication with AI tools, information verification, and technology operation tend to blend in practice. The scale should therefore reflect these natural “hybrid” skill areas rather than forcing them into strict boxes.
2. Second, the *language used in the scale must be familiar and straightforward*. Many participants among PRODIGI vulnerable groups, across different age groups and backgrounds, found technical or academic terms confusing. Terms such as “algorithm,” “framework,” “multimodal,” and even “bias” were often unclear; therefore, the scale should include everyday alternatives, such as “unfair treatment” or “fake video,” and provide clear explanations of concepts that may be unfamiliar to some users.
3. Third, *it is important that the questions feel relevant to people’s real lives*. Young people connect best with examples involving social media, homework help, or creative tasks, whereas older adults relate more to everyday activities such as finding recipes, writing messages, or checking opening hours. Questions that assume prior knowledge, such as programming skills or an understanding of plagiarism, should be included only if they are explained.
4. Fourth, *the scale must also stay focused and easy to complete*. Removing overlapping questions and avoiding items that ask two things at once will help prevent confusion and reduce respondent burden.
5. Finally, *users’ voices must guide the design*. Throughout the research, experts often considered certain items clear, whereas participants found them confusing. In these cases, user feedback should inform decision-making. This approach helps ensure that the scale reflects the real experiences, needs, and abilities of the people it is intended to serve, particularly vulnerable groups such as refugees, older adults, and students in vocational pathways.

2. About the PRODIGI Project

Misinformation and disinformation pose significant contemporary challenges, affecting individuals and societies alike. Their consequences are particularly harmful in high-stakes domains such as public health, where false information has been associated with risky behaviours, lower vaccination uptake, and heightened anxiety and depression. Beyond individual harms, misinformation can erode trust in journalism, science, and public institutions, thereby weakening the shared informational foundations that democratic societies rely on. These risks have intensified as AI technologies increasingly shape how content is produced and consumed. Deepfakes can convincingly fabricate audio-visual “evidence,” and widely used conversational chatbots can generate fluent, authoritative-sounding text at scale, making misleading narratives easier to create, adapt, and circulate rapidly while obscuring provenance and accountability.

In this context, AI literacy becomes directly relevant to misinformation resilience not simply as technical familiarity, but as a set of competencies that help people recognise how AI systems generate and prioritise content, understand their limitations (e.g., hallucinations, bias, and opacity), and apply appropriate verification strategies. Recognising that AI and digital literacy are not standalone solutions, this project approaches AI literacy as a multifaceted capability that combines critical judgement (e.g., source evaluation, detection of manipulation, etc.) with operational skills (e.g., using tools and settings safely and effectively). This is especially important for at-risk populations who face digital disparities and may have fewer resources to verify information, making targeted AI literacy efforts a necessary component of broader responses to AI-amplified misinformation.

PRODIGI investigates AI literacy and digital skills within the context of vulnerability, focusing on three demographic groups: unaccompanied minors in Belgian refugee centres, economically disadvantaged youth in Portuguese vocational education, and elderly individuals in Polish small cities and rural areas.

Objectives

PRODIGI’s key objectives are as follows:

1. **To assess AI Literacy and Digital Skills** using performance tests in three different countries: Belgium, Portugal, and Poland. This assessment involves three distinct target groups. In Belgium, we will focus on unaccompanied minors and their guardians/youth workers. In Portugal, our attention will be on children and young individuals from socio-economically disadvantaged families enrolled in professional education programmes. In this context, we will also involve their teachers/trainers. Finally, in Poland, we will focus on elderly residents of rural areas who receive assistance from pre-teachers in lifelong learning centres. This intergenerational contact will facilitate the use of digital media and promote AI literacy among older people. We aim to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of AI literacy and digital skills intervention (with a focus on mis- and disinformation) within these diverse groups, taking into account the unique contexts and requirements of each country.
2. Following this, we will work together with members of the target populations and individuals in caregiving roles to **collaboratively improve relevant existing intervention programmes**. We will then design, develop, and implement targeted interventions and assess its effectiveness through pre- and post-tests.
3. Furthermore, we will **create a resilience toolkit tailored explicitly for the implementation** of pre- and post-tests, enabling the measurement of intervention programme outcomes. This

toolkit will place a particular focus on AI literacy and non-technical critical skills, including an understanding of mis- and disinformation resilience operations.

4. Lastly, in cooperation with the EDMO regional hubs, the Media & Learning Association, and the Euromedia Research Group, which will facilitate our engagement with mainstream information media, we will actively ***transform our research findings into recommendations for both practice and policy***, aligning them with the policies of individual countries and the European Union. PRODIGI responds to policymakers' growing interest in leveraging media literacy/ AI literacy to combat the adverse impacts of digital communication technologies. PRODIGI aims to contribute to evidence-based policymaking and safeguarding democratic values.

PRODIGI consortium

The strength of the PRODIGI team lies in its diverse capabilities, aligned with the project’s scientific and policy-relevant objectives. PRODIGI brings together three academic partners – KU Leuven (coordinator), Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, and Jagiellonian University in Kraków. The project runs from 2025 to 2027 and is coordinated and led at KU Leuven by Prof. Leen d’Haenens and Dr. Tania Azadi, with Prof. Łukasz Tomczyk from Jagiellonian University in Kraków and Prof. Cristina Ponte from Universidade NOVA de Lisboa as beneficiaries and co-leaders. In addition to their academic work, the partners have contributed research and policy reports to national, European, and international institutions, including the European Commission and several national governments. The PRODIGI team is structured to address all research themes explored in the project, drawing on extensive academic expertise and diverse disciplinary approaches. Partners have previously collaborated on various projects (ySKILLS, REMEDIS, EU Kids Online) and will once again participate together in all WPs. This collaborative approach fosters strong synergies among the different WPs. In establishing the consortium, we aimed to achieve complementary geographic representation across the EU, with partners from Belgium, Poland, and Portugal. In addition, a PRODIGI advisory board has been established, bringing together experts with relevant subject-matter expertise.

Name And Function	Organisation	Role/Tasks/Professional Profile And Expertise
<u>Leen d’Haenens</u> , Full professor		Project coordinator, WP1 & WP5 leader, Youth and digital media, Impact measurement of media literacy and digital skills intervention programmes, Measuring diversity in media, Narratives on migration, Attitudes towards migration.
<u>Tania Azadi</u> , Postdoc researcher		Senior researcher & project manager. Expert in media and information literacy assessment, information seeking behaviour, information evaluation behaviour, interventional study design, participatory design, refugee youth.
<u>Ans De Nolf</u> , Postdoc researcher		Researcher. Expert in Islamophobia among young people and vulnerable groups.
<u>Verónica Donoso</u> , Postdoc researcher		Senior researcher specialising in digital and media literacy, online safety and the well-being of youth in digital environments.
<u>Cristina Ponte</u> , Full professor		WP4 leader. Vulnerable youth, education and digital media. Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation resources.
<u>Susana Batista</u> , Associate professor		Researcher. Expert in sociology of education, educational inequality, and youth and media research.
<u>Estrella Luna</u> , Postdoc researcher		Researcher and trainer. Expert in education and Media and Information Literacy with young people and vulnerable groups. Implementation of the student’s training and teachers’ training.

Marisa Torres da Silva,
Full professor

Senior researcher. Expert in hate speech and disinformation, news media consumption, media diversity, and news literacy.

Lukasz Tomczyk,
Associate professor

WP2 & WP3 leader. Management of the Polish research team. Coordinates and prepares measurement tools for modules 1-3 (Polish team interventions), coordinates recruitment of participants, quality control of intervention implementation, preparation of trainers, and co-leads activities. Collaborates with local institutions involved in senior education.

Magdalena Żegleń,
Postdoc researcher

Researcher. Expert in developmental and health-related psychology with a focus on child and adolescent physical and behavioural outcomes.

3. Introduction

Artificial intelligence is no longer a distant, futuristic technology; it is woven into nearly every aspect of our daily lives. Its impact extends far beyond technology: in health, AI supports medical diagnosis and personalised treatment and shapes how we manage our well-being. In society, it influences how we access information, communicate, and interact with institutions. In education, it changes how we learn, teach, and evaluate knowledge. Economically, it reshapes labour markets, creates new opportunities, but also new inequalities. From an environmental perspective, the energy consumption of AI systems has a growing global footprint. These impacts are complex and interconnected, influencing individual behaviours, social structures, and policy landscapes. Because AI affects how we understand, act, and make decisions, being able to critically and responsibly use, understand, and evaluate AI systems is no longer optional; it is essential.

This is why developing a robust, validated AI literacy scale is important: it helps measure individuals' knowledge. It can do when navigating AI-driven environments, and how prepared they are to address the opportunities and risks associated with it. However, many existing assessment frameworks and scales on AI literacy have limitations. They are often tested on dominant populations (e.g., the general public or university students, particularly in medical or technical fields) rather than vulnerable or underrepresented groups. Many frameworks are derived from literature reviews and validated quantitatively, sometimes complemented by expert opinion, but they often fail to address the specific needs of their target populations. In addition, a few adopt a Participatory Action Research (PAR) or co-design approach that involves direct stakeholders in the development process. Many focus primarily on usage, attitudes, outcomes, or confidence, rather than assessing actual skills; that is, what people are demonstrably able to do.

Vulnerable groups often face barriers to accessing and understanding digital information, which exacerbates existing inequalities (Azadi, d'Haenens, & Azadi, 2025; Azadi, d'Haenens, Donoso, & Waechter, 2025). Therefore, mapping AI literacy and digital skills in contexts of vulnerability is an important first step in co-constructing responsive interventions that address the specific needs and experiences of these groups.

Whereas existing AI literacy scales primarily capture young people's self-perceived abilities, the PRODIGI project assesses demonstrated skills and critical understanding. This is particularly urgent in an environment where algorithmic systems and generative AI increasingly shape how information is produced, distributed, and consumed. To address this gap, this report introduces an assessment framework that integrates AI literacy into the Youth Digital Skills Indicator (yDSI) conceptualisation, developed by Helsper et al. (2020) under the H2020-[ySKILLS](#) project (2020-2023). Our tool aims to measure foundational AI literacy competencies and critical AI skills, which are much needed when navigating the online world.

This report details the development, co-design, piloting, and validation of this scale within the context of PRODIGI's target groups: unaccompanied minor refugees in Belgium, students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds in Portugal, and elderly individuals in Poland.

4. Methodology

PRODIGI AI literacy definition and conceptualisation

To define **AI literacy**, it is essential first to clarify what literacy itself means. Traditionally, literacy has been defined as “*the ability to express ourselves and communicate using written language*” (Freire, 1972). As Freire (1972) argues, fostering literacy carries significant political and historical implications, as it broadens access to knowledge and empowers individuals to share and communicate ideas. Literacy, therefore, is not merely a technical skill but a transformative social practice that shapes how individuals participate in society.

In practice, literacy has been operationalised as *a set of competencies including knowledge, skills, and attitudes that collectively enable expression, communication, and access to knowledge*. Over time, the notion of literacy has evolved beyond reading and writing to encompass the ability to navigate and make meaning from diverse symbolic and technological systems. The concept of literacy has since been applied across a wide range of domains that share the potential to enhance human expression, communication, and access to knowledge.

These include:

- **Information literacy**, which involves “*the ability to recognise when information is needed and to locate, evaluate, and use that information effectively and ethically*” (American Library Association, 1989; UNESCO, 2013).
- **Media literacy**, understood as “*the ability to access, analyse, evaluate, and create media in a variety of forms, and to understand how media messages shape perceptions and culture*” (Potter, 2019; UNESCO, 2011).
- **Digital literacy**, defined as “*the ability to use information and communication technologies to find, evaluate, create, and communicate information, requiring both cognitive and technical skills*” (Law, 2018).
- **Data literacy**, defined as “*the ability to read, work with, analyse, and communicate data, enabling individuals to make evidence-based decisions*” (Carlson et al., 2011).
- **Digital platforms literacy**, referring to “*the ability to effectively and responsibly use, manage, and evaluate content on social networking platforms, with an understanding of their algorithms, affordances, and social implications*” (Ha & Kim, 2024).

Each of these literacies reflects a growing recognition that in a digital and data-driven society, individuals must not only consume information but also critically evaluate, produce, and engage with knowledge systems.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has also been defined as a “*machine-based system that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments*” (OECD, 2024). Today, the term “AI” typically refers to a broad range of AI systems, including predictive and generative systems (e.g., ChatGPT).

Within the PRODIGI project, we understand AI literacy as *a set of competencies that enable individuals to communicate, work, and live effectively with both other people and intelligent machines*. In particular, it enables individuals to engage with, create with, and manage it while critically evaluating its benefits, risks, and ethical implications. Due to the rapid public uptake and everyday availability of

generative AI tools and their direct relevance to information quality and misinformation risks we focused primarily on generative AI applications such as large language model chatbots (e.g., ChatGPT and similar systems), text-to-image generators, and deepfake or synthetic media tools.

This definition also extends the traditional scope of literacy to encompass human-AI interaction. Similarly, Long and Magerko (2020) conceptualise AI literacy as “a set of competencies that enables individuals to evaluate AI technologies critically; communicate and collaborate effectively with AI; and use AI as a tool online, at home, and in the workplace.” Their definition underscores the multidimensional nature of AI literacy, combining functional, critical, and ethical aspects of engagement with intelligent technologies.

AI literacy is clearly related to other, previously established literacies, most notably digital literacy, and can be viewed as an extension of it (Yang, 2022). *Digital literacy is a prerequisite for AI literacy*, as individuals must first understand how to use digital technologies (e.g., computers, online platforms, and applications) to find, evaluate, create, and communicate information in order to make sense of and engage meaningfully with AI systems.

Building on this foundation, we draw on the Youth Digital Skills Indicator (yDSI) framework as a validated, empirically grounded model for structuring the competencies that constitute AI literacy (Helsper et al., 2020). The yDSI provides a unique, cross-nationally validated measurement tool that distinguishes between digital skills and digital knowledge items and can be used in large-scale population research. Accordingly, we construct our AI literacy competencies (skills and critical knowledge) around the four core dimensions of digital skills identified in the yDSI framework.

1. **Technical and operational skills**, including operating, connecting, and customising subcomponents
2. **Information navigation and processing skills**, including navigating, interpreting, and evaluating subcomponents
3. **Communication and interaction skills**, including managing, protecting, and netiquette subcomponents
4. **Content creation and production skills**, including producing, attracting, and understanding subcomponents

Additionally, through the literature review we identified a fifth dimension i.e., ethics and responsible use of AI which we incorporated into our conceptualisation alongside the four original yDSI dimensions.

5. **Ethical and responsible use of AI**, including fairness, transparency, accountability, privacy, sustainability, and societal impact

In this report, we describe the methodology we used to develop and validate our scale, the Youth AI Literacy Scale (yAILS) as well as the Senior AI Literacy Scale (sAILS). yAILS and sAILS hold the promise to be a valid and reliable assessment tool to assess AI literacy of youth and seniors. This scale tries to address the existing inequalities in communication research and in knowledge production within the field by co-designing and co-validating the tool across the vulnerable and marginalised groups (unaccompanied minor and refugee youth as well seniors).

Co-designing and co-validating the AI Literacy Scale with vulnerable youth and seniors is a deliberate effort to ensure that the tool is both inclusive and contextually relevant. By involving disadvantaged youth, refugee youth and seniors (PRODIGI target groups) in the development process, we aim to capture diverse lived experiences and to avoid reproducing dominant cultural biases that are often embedded in standardised assessments. This participatory approach empowers our young and elderly participants as co-creators of knowledge, promotes equity in communication research, and enhances the scale's validity across different social and cultural contexts. It also aligns with ethical research practices by respecting the agency of those whose realities the scale seeks to measure (Moll et al., 2020; Mulvale et al., 2019; Peters et al., 2024).

Developed using best-practice frameworks for scale development, the scale is grounded in rigorous design principles and adheres to established validation standards, including assessments of criterion, convergent, and discriminant validity. This approach addresses limitations in individual tools and enhances the scale's applicability to diverse populations, enabling meaningful comparisons across groups. A distinctive contribution of yAILS is its explicit inclusion of the ethical and responsible use of AI, a dimension often neglected as a separate domain in current assessments.

In parallel with the development of the Youth AI Literacy Scale (yAILS), the PRODIGI project has initiated the development of the Senior AI Literacy Scale (sAILS). Building on the conceptual framework, item pool, and validation strategy of yAILS, sAILS is being adapted to reflect the specific life contexts, usage patterns, and learning trajectories of older adults. Particular attention is paid to differences in cognitive load, digital experience, accessibility needs, and everyday AI encounters that are especially salient for senior populations (e.g., voice assistants, recommender systems, and AI-supported public and health services).

The development of sAILS follows the same best-practice principles of inclusive and participatory scale construction that underpin yAILS. Professionals working with older adults were actively involved through interviews and cognitive testing to assess item clarity, relevance, and interpretability, thereby ensuring that the scale captures meaningful dimensions of AI literacy without relying on age-biased assumptions or deficit-oriented framings. This co-design and co-validation process aims to avoid reproducing generational biases commonly found in digital skills assessments and to foreground seniors' experiential knowledge and practical competencies.

Preliminary analyses focus on evaluating the feasibility of a shortened and accessible version of the scale that balances psychometric robustness with practical constraints related to survey length and respondent burden. Ongoing validation work examines reliability, factor structure, and measurement equivalence across age groups, laying the groundwork for future comparative analyses between youth and senior populations. Through this parallel and aligned development process, sAILS extends the PRODIGI project's commitment to inclusive, context-sensitive, and ethically grounded measurement of AI literacy across the life course.

AI Literacy Scale Design

We followed the best practices for developing and validating scales for health, social, and behavioural research developed by Boateng et al. (2018), which acts as the gold standard in the domain of scale development and validation. There are three phases to creating a rigorous scale. They include **item development, scale development, and scale evaluation**. In the following sections, we describe the procedures and steps undertaken to develop and validate the yAILS.

Item and Scale Development Phase

Two main activities in item development are domain identification and item generation, followed by expert and target population evaluation (Boateng et al., 2018). We applied a combined deductive and inductive approach to identify our domains or dimensions and to generate items. We rely on the four dimensions (domains) of the cross-country-validated yDSI framework, the literature we reviewed, and interviews with 15 youth (ages 13-17), including four with lower socioeconomic status, to identify the fifth dimension. That also shaped part of our co-design approach toward the yAILS item development and domain identification.

Instead of introducing yet another standalone instrument, yAILS builds on the strengths of previously validated AI literacy measures to provide a more comprehensive and robust assessment tool. By integrating well-established items from existing scales, yAILS ensures broad content coverage and capitalises on the proven validity of prior instruments. We built upon a systematic review of AI literacy scales (Lintner, 2024), which identified 22 studies validating 16 scales targeting various populations, including the general population, higher education students, secondary education students, and teachers. Due to the limited number of studies focusing on children and youth, we also considered other validated scales developed for other populations. These 16 scales were included because they generally demonstrated good structural validity and internal consistency.

The review by Lintner was conducted up until 2024, so to cover the literature published after 2024 we conducted a *rapid literature review* in accordance with established guidance for streamlined evidence synthesis (Tapia-Benavente et al., 2021). This method was particularly appropriate for the rapidly evolving field of AI literacy, where new frameworks and assessment tools are continually developed (Cotilla & Esther, 2025). Using this approach, we obtained a clear picture of what is already known and identified the key ideas that should inform the development of a new AI literacy scale, particularly for vulnerable or underserved communities.

The literature search was conducted across several major academic databases, including WOS, Scopus and ACM Digital Library and relevant reliable reports, including the UNESCO AI Competency Framework, the OECD Artificial Intelligence Principles, and the European Union’s Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. Search terms combined descriptors related to artificial intelligence literacy, digital competence, algorithmic literacy, computational thinking, responsible AI, and assessment. The initial search produced 1595 records. These records were screened in two stages after deduplication (n=341). First, titles and abstracts were reviewed to exclude publications that did not address AI literacy scales, questionnaires, or assessment instruments. Full-text screening was then conducted using predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria based on the PRODIGI–AI Literacy Scale Scoping Review protocol. To be included, studies had to present the development, adaptation, or validation of an AI literacy scale or measurement tool and report empirical, quantitative, or mixed-method data. Eligible studies were required to provide at least one form of validity evidence (such as content, construct, convergent, discriminant, or criterion validity) and at least one reliability measure, including internal consistency metrics (e.g., Cronbach’s alpha), composite reliability, or test–retest reliability.

Publications also had to be peer-reviewed, written in English, and published from 2024 onward. Studies were excluded (n=1169) if they:

- consisted solely of conceptual or theoretical discussions of AI literacy;
- contained educational interventions without psychometric testing; qualitative studies that did not generate a quantitative measurement instrument;
- reported on tools assessing general digital, media, or information literacy without a specific AI focus; public opinion polls lacking psychometric evidence;
- or were duplicate or incomplete records, such as preprints without peer review or abstracts without full text.

In total, 42 studies met the criteria and were included in the review.

From these studies and supplementary grey literature, we identified 18 existing AI literacy and AI-related competence scales. An overview of these items and thematic categories is provided in Appendix A. Items and thematic categories from each scale were extracted and mapped onto the four dimensions defined by the yDSI framework. This process identified 307 initial items later on refined to 60 items aligned with the operational, informational, communicative, and content creation dimensions of the yDSI. These items included both skill-based and knowledge-based components and represented current thinking about what young people need to understand and be able to do when interacting with AI systems.

During the conceptual mapping process, it became clear that ethical and responsible engagement with AI technologies is essential to AI understanding. Constructs such as fairness, transparency, accountability, privacy, sustainability, and societal impact appeared consistently across guidance from international organisations, including the UNESCO AI Competency Framework, the OECD Artificial Intelligence Principles, and the European Union’s Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI. These concepts were not fully represented in the original four-dimensional yDSI framework. Given their prominence in modern discussions of AI literacy and their relevance to safe and informed participation in digital societies, we added a fifth dimension to the developing scale: Ethical and Responsible AI Use. This new dimension added 12 items, covering the responsibilities, risks, and broader societal implications associated with AI. This dimension, although not part of the original yDSI framework, was considered crucial for capturing the specific challenges and responsibilities associated with the use of AI systems in contemporary society.

Question and Answer Scale Formulation of the Skill Items

We also followed the wording of the questions in accordance with the yDSI guideline. The original question asks:

“Please indicate how true the following statements are of you when thinking about how you use the internet and technologies such as mobile phones or computers. Reply, thinking about how true this would be of you if you had to do it now, on your own. If you do not understand what the question is asking, tick the box “I do not understand what you mean by this”

To align the item with the assessment of AI-related skills, references to general digital technologies were replaced by *AI tools (e.g., chatbots, image generators, voice assistants)*. All items are scored on a Likert-type scale measuring self-perceived skill proficiency:

- Not at all true of me
- Not very true of me
- Neither true nor untrue of me
- Mostly true of me
- Very true of me
- I do not understand what you mean by this
- I do not want to answer

Question and Answer Scale Formulation of the Knowledge Items

For the knowledge items, similarly, we followed the wording of the questions in accordance with the yDSI guideline. The original question asks:

“To what extent are the following statements about technologies such as the internet and mobile phones true or not true? If you are not sure, please let us know”.

In order to adapt the question to our scale objective, which assesses skills in relation to AI, we changed the phrase “technologies such as the internet and mobile phones” to “AI tools, such as chatbots (like ChatGPT), image generators (like DALL-E), or voice assistants (like Siri or Google Assistant)”.

Scale Evaluation Phase

To assess whether the 60 items adequately measure the five dimensions of interest, we conducted two types of evaluation: expert evaluation and evaluation by our target population. Expert evaluation was conducted by expert judgments using an online survey, and target population evaluation was conducted using cognitive interviews with disadvantaged youth, refugee youth, as well as seniors. The methodology and results of expert evaluation and cognitive interviews have been provided in the next sections per each participating country.

To complement these qualitative stages, a pilot study was conducted in which the initial version of the scale was administered to young people in Belgium (n=1200). This pilot provided preliminary quantitative evidence regarding item performance, internal consistency, and the emerging factor structure. It also allowed us to test administrative procedures and evaluate the instrument's ability to capture variation in literacy levels within an at-risk population. In what follows, we will detail the methodology for each of the three research contexts.

1. Belgian context

Expert consultation

To strengthen the development of the PRODIGI AI Literacy Scale, we collected expert feedback via an online survey. The goal was to evaluate the clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of the draft scale items and to gather suggestions for improvement before further testing with young people and other target groups. Experts were invited to participate based on their experience in AI literacy, digital literacy, media education, and educational assessment. Invitations were sent by email to five experts in digital skills, of whom three responded and agreed to participate in the survey, and included a link to the survey, along with a brief explanation of the project’s goals and the purpose of the scale. Participation was voluntary.

For each item, experts were asked to rate how relevant the statement was for measuring different dimensions of AI literacy and how clear the wording was. Both ratings used a four-point scale ranging from low to high. In addition to these quantitative ratings, open-ended comment boxes enabled experts to explain their reasoning, identify ambiguous or unclear wording, suggest alternative formulations, or flag missing concepts that should be included in the scale. In total, the survey produced both structured ratings and qualitative comments. These responses were systematically reviewed to identify patterns, such as items consistently rated as unclear, items considered highly relevant, and areas in which experts recommended revisions to improve the scale's overall structure.

Overall, they stressed that the assessment should be easy to understand across diverse cultural and linguistic contexts and should be developed in collaboration with the users to ensure it remains clear and relevant. A detailed analysis is provided in the next section, which presents the findings.

Cognitive interviews with vulnerable youth

Six cognitive interviews were conducted with five 17-year-old boys from Afghanistan, Syria, and Eritrea and one 15-year-old from Afghanistan. An overview of all informants is provided in Table 1. Interviews were conducted at Refugee Centre Fedasil Overijse, in Belgium on 26/11/2025 by two researchers.

Table 1: Overview of informants

Participant	Gender	Age	Nationality	Interviewed by
1	Boy	17	Afghanistan	Researcher 1
2	Boy	17	Syria	Researcher 1
3	Boy	17	Eritrea	Researcher 1
4	Boy	15	Afghanistan	Researcher 2
5	Boy	17	Syria	Researcher 2
6	Boy	17	Afghanistan	Researcher 2

Researcher 1 had access to a private room to conduct the interviews. She conducted the interviews in English and had a translator present for three of them. Researcher 2 interviewed in an open area accessible to both residents of the refugee centre and personnel. During these interviews, there was movement and interaction among people. This affected the concentration levels of both the children and the researcher. Despite this, three interviews could be finalised.

Both researchers obtained participants' consent to audio-record the interviews. The boys interviewed by researcher 1 consented to the recordings, whereas researcher 2 could not record due to the interviewees' preference; therefore, only handwritten notes were taken during the interviews.

The research team presented participants with the entire set of scale visual cards from which to choose. The cards were printed in different background colours representing the different item categories of the scale. Researchers gave participants complete agency as regards which cards they chose. This helped make participants feel at ease, which in turn facilitated the interviewing process. In total, 15 items were tested in English and 16 in Dutch, with one item tested twice in Dutch.

Two of the three children interviewed first observed the cards laid out on the table, selected one, looked at it, and either kept it or discarded it. When asked why some cards were being discarded, participants consistently responded that the question was too long. Sometimes they added that the question was difficult or that they did not understand it, and therefore preferred to choose another card.

Overall, the interviews showed that many young people found technical terms such as “algorithm,” “bias,” “multi-modal,” “framework,” “deepfake”, etc. difficult, struggled with long or abstract sentences, and were confused by questions that did not align with their everyday experiences or perceived skills. A detailed analysis is provided in the next section, which presents the findings.

Pilot survey testing

To assess how well the emerging AI literacy framework functioned in practice, we conducted a pilot survey among secondary school students (n=1200; age: 16–18) in Flanders, Belgium to explore whether the structure of traditional digital skills models could adequately capture the competencies required for interacting with AI systems. Earlier frameworks, such as the yDSI within ySKILLS, were designed for environments in which people worked with digital tools rather than intelligent agents. In those contexts, skills could be measured separately because tasks such as searching for information, navigating interfaces, adjusting settings, communicating, or creating content typically unfolded in clear, modular steps. However, AI systems break this modularity. Interacting with chatbots, multimodal generators, or recommendation engines requires users to interpret information, communicate effectively, exercise creativity, and make ethical judgments simultaneously. For example, writing an effective prompt requires both linguistic clarity and creative thinking, whereas evaluating AI outputs involves ongoing attention to fairness, accuracy, and potential biases, as well as concerns such as cognitive offloading, attention fragmentation, and reduced originality (Thaker et al, 2025). These overlapping cognitive demands mean that the skill areas traditionally treated as distinct (creativity, communication, information evaluation, and ethics) become closely intertwined during AI use (Shippee, 2024). Our pilot testing, therefore, examined how these competencies emerged together within real interactions with AI systems, revealing a more hybrid factor structure than that found in classical digital skills models. Rather than reflecting isolated task categories, the resulting domains of AI literacy capture the lived experience of engaging with generative AI, in which interpretation, co-creation, and ethical reasoning unfold simultaneously.

The first exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted on split sample 1 and yielded a four-factor solution. This solution was retained as the initial measurement model for the newly developed scale because it provided the clearest and most interpretable structure, with comparatively fewer problematic cross-loadings and less conceptual overlap between factors than alternative solutions. Items clustered into four meaningful components: Factor 1 (Content Creation and Communication), Factor 2 (Ethics), Factor 3 (Information Navigation), and Factor 4 (Technical/Operational). This differs from earlier models and reflects how young people actually use AI. The study also found that many

participants had limited knowledge about how AI functions. A detailed analysis is provided in the next section, which presents the findings.

2. Portuguese context

Expert consultation and cognitive interviews

An expert review was conducted to assess the clarity, relevance, and age-appropriateness of our AI Literacy Scale for youth enrolled in a range of vocational programmes. Four expert reviewers, comprising AI specialists, teacher educators, and digital literacy practitioners, were recruited to examine each survey item and provide detailed qualitative feedback. Reviewers received the draft scale along with guidance prompts inviting them to comment on terminology, conceptual alignment with curriculum objectives, potential misunderstandings, and any perceived redundancy among items.

Experts annotated the items directly and submitted written commentary. Their observations were then consolidated into an analytic memo synthesising recurring themes, including problematic jargon (e.g., “frameworks”, “multimodal prompting”), unfamiliar or abstract terms (e.g., *fidedigna*, *enviesamento*), and items requiring contextualization or definition. Reviewers also flagged age-inappropriate content (e.g., assumptions about prior programming knowledge or plagiarism) and identified overlapping material across sections. This feedback was systematically coded and used to generate item-level recommendations. The expert review served as the first stage of the co-design validation process, informing revisions prior to youth cognitive testing.

The implementation and analysis of the cognitive interviews was guided by Haddon and Ponte (2012) and draws on annotations generated during cognitive testing sessions with 10 Portuguese students. The students were enrolled in a range of vocational programmes: Performative Arts, Cooking, Socio-Cultural Mediation, Legal Assistance, Child Care Support and Sports Training. Two of them had a Venezuelan background. Feedback from both groups contributed important perspectives on item clarity, accessibility, and perceived relevance. Throughout the analysis, illustrative examples and quotations from student participants are used to highlight recurring concerns, such as requests for more precise terminology or for identifying items that were confusing or overly complex. These insights informed the item-level recommendations and helped ensure that the scale is both valid and responsive to youth perspectives.

3. Polish context

Expert consultation

To better understand how digital tools for older adults can be improved, particularly in the context of rapidly evolving technologies and AI, the Polish research team conducted a qualitative study using expert interviews. The study took place in the second half of November 2025 and was conducted online.

Several well-known Polish specialists in digital education for older adults were invited to participate. These experts were selected because they have extensive experience in training older adults, advising organisations, and conducting academic research on digital inclusion. Each expert took part in a semi-structured interview. This format allowed the Polish team to explore recurring themes while also giving participants the freedom to expand on their experiences and insights. With consent, all interviews were recorded and transcribed.

The interview data were analysed using thematic analysis, which enabled the identification of recurring topics, concerns, and recommendations (Ahmed et al., 2025). Through this process, the Polish team identified key themes, including the need for simple, clear language in diagnostic tools, the importance of avoiding overly technical or lengthy assessments that may overwhelm older adults, and the value of using real-life situations that are familiar and practical for older adults. Points of agreement among experts, as well as the most frequently mentioned challenges and solutions, were highlighted during the analysis.

By bringing together experts' hands-on experience and existing knowledge from adult education and learning in later life, the Polish team gained a clearer picture of what older adults need from digital assessment tools. The themes that emerged from the interviews informed practical recommendations to make future tools easier to understand, less cognitively demanding, and better suited to the real challenges seniors face when using digital technologies and AI in their everyday lives.

Ethical Considerations and Governance

The development and planned validation of the γ AALS and sAALS adheres to rigorous ethical standards appropriate for research involving minors and vulnerable populations. Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Social and Societal Ethics Committee (SMEC) at KU Leuven, Belgium (G-2025-10348). The research protocol, including recruitment procedures, consent materials, and data handling plans, was reviewed by the committee to ensure compliance with KU Leuven institutional and international research ethics guidelines for research involving children and youth.

Special attention was given to informed consent and assent procedures. All participants under the age of 18 were asked to provide assent, while their legal guardians was required to provide informed consent too. For refugee youth and unaccompanied minors, additional safeguards was implemented in collaboration with care institutions (e.g., Fedasil) and legal representatives to ensure ethical participation and comprehension of study procedures such as having a trusted guardian/social worker present or available during the session, using age-appropriate and plain-language information sheets and verbally checking understanding (e.g., asking participants to explain in their own words what participation involved), emphasising voluntariness and the right to stop or skip questions at any time without consequences for services or support, and ensuring privacy and confidentiality by conducting interviews in a safe space and limiting access to identifiable data to authorised research staff only. Participation was voluntary, and all participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without any negative consequences. They were also reminded of this right during the session, and were encouraged to take breaks, skip questions, or stop the interview whenever they felt tired or uncomfortable. Beverages and small snacks were provided throughout the sessions to support participants' comfort.

Confidentiality was strictly maintained throughout the study. Personally identifiable information was not collected, and all responses was anonymised prior to analysis. Data was stored securely on encrypted servers managed by KU Leuven (e.g., ManGo), with access restricted to authorised research personnel only. Backup procedures and data retention policies complied with GDPR standards. This ethical framework ensures that the rights, dignity, and safety of all participants, especially those from vulnerable and marginalised groups, are protected throughout the research process.

Limitations

While the scale has been developed through a rigorous test-theoretical framework and co-designed with vulnerable populations, some limitations should be acknowledged :

- **Context-Specific Design:** Items were co-developed with youth in specific cultural and educational contexts. While efforts were made to ensure inclusivity (like a pilot test with 1200 children in 5th and 6th years of secondary school in Flanders, Belgium), the scale may require adaptation for use in other regions or populations.
- **Language and Literacy Constraints:** Although the scale was designed for youth aged 14–19, variations in reading level, language proficiency, and digital exposure may affect item comprehension in some subgroups.
- **Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Independent Validation:** Finally, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) has yet to be conducted; therefore, the stability and fit of the factor model should be tested in an independent sample before the structure is considered definitive.

5. Findings

This section summarises our findings while testing and improving the AI Literacy Scale (yAILS and sAILS) in Belgium, Portugal, and Poland. We combined survey data from 1,200 young people with feedback from experts, students, and senior learners. In Belgium, we analysed survey responses to see how different AI skills naturally group together. In Portugal and Poland, we examined how clear, relevant, and realistic the questions were for young people and older adults with very different language and digital skills.

Together, these findings indicate which parts of the scale perform well, which questions are confusing or repetitive, and how AI skills are used in everyday life. They also guide the simplification and shortening of the scale and its alignment with EU digital education goals, so that it can be used reliably with diverse groups of learners.

1. Belgian context

Expert consultation

An expert review was conducted to evaluate the Youth AI Literacy Scale (yAILS), focusing on the clarity and relevance of sixty statements designed to measure AI literacy in young people. Three experts rated each item on a four-point scale for both relevance and clarity and provided optional qualitative comments. The purpose of this analysis was to assess the overall scale strength, identify items requiring revision, and determine whether the current set of statements appropriately reflects key aspects of AI literacy.

Main findings

Relevance

The expert feedback on the relevance of the questions in the Youth AI Literacy Scale (yAILS) focused heavily on item redundancy, the categorisation of specific skills, and the practical likelihood that users would perform the described tasks. Overall, the experts rated the scale's content as highly relevant. The average relevance score across all items was 3.28 out of 4, and more than 80% of ratings fell within the two highest categories (3 or 4). This indicates that the reviewers agree that the scale successfully captures important concepts within AI literacy. Statements addressing foundational ideas (such as the possibility that AI systems may generate harmful content, mix true and false information, or provide different outputs to different users) received the highest ratings for both relevance and clarity.

Clarity

Clarity ratings for the Youth AI Literacy Scale (yAILS), while generally positive, showed greater variability than relevance ratings, with an average score of 2.89 out of 4 and notably more evaluations falling into the lower clarity categories. This indicates that, although the content is broadly appropriate, the wording of many items remains somewhat complex, academic, or ambiguous for the target youth audience, including teenagers, refugees, and individuals with low digital literacy. Reviewers frequently noted that vocabulary such as “integrate,” “insights,” “neutral,” and “comprehensive understanding” was overly advanced, while technical terms like “multimodal,” “frameworks,” and “programming languages” were likely to be misunderstood. Items with the lowest clarity scores commonly included abstract phrasing, lengthy or multi-part sentence structures, or

unclear concepts such as “*fair and unfair mistakes*,” distinctions between “*information*” and “*content*,” and references to “*human bias*” without explanation.

A source of confusion stemmed from items that combined multiple actions, such as “*check and adjust*” privacy settings, “*recognise and improve*” prompts, or “*plan or create*” with AI, which made it difficult for respondents to answer accurately. Vagueness also contributed to lower clarity, with reviewers questioning unclear outcomes (“*so I do not have problems*”), broad terms (“*projects and applications*”), and ambiguous distinctions between “*AI tools*,” “*AI apps*,” and “*AI systems*.” To enhance clarity, reviewers recommended simplifying vocabulary, splitting multi-part questions, replacing jargon (e.g., “*write stories*” or “*creative writing or storytelling*”), adding familiar examples (e.g., “*Siri*” for voice assistants), and refining phrasing to better match youth comprehension.

Areas of improvement

When providing qualitative feedback, experts consistently identified several key areas for strengthening the Youth AI Literacy Scale (yAILS) to better align with the needs and abilities of the target audience. A recurring concern was the repetition and overlap among items related to evaluating AI-generated information, detecting misinformation or bias, and deciding whether to accept or reject AI outputs. Although these are central components of AI literacy, their appearance across multiple similarly worded statements risks redundancy, reduces conceptual clarity, and may contribute to respondent fatigue. Simplifying, merging, or removing repetitive items would help streamline the instrument and enhance its focus.

Experts also underscored the importance of simplifying vocabulary, noting that numerous terms were excessively academic or abstract for young audiences, including refugees and individuals with limited digital literacy. Words such as integrate, insights, and comprehensive understanding were flagged as unnecessarily complex, with reviewers recommending simpler alternatives, such as combine, information, or better understanding. Similarly, terms such as fairness, credit, and responsibility were considered too academic, while technical jargon, such as “multimodal”, “frameworks”, and “programming languages” was viewed as inaccessible for the intended population. Even the commonly used term “prompts” was questioned, with experts suggesting that youth may understand phrases such as “questions,” “asking better questions,” or “getting better answers” more easily. Abstract concepts, including human bias or descriptors such as neutral, were deemed unclear without explanation; reviewers recommended alternatives, such as balanced or fair.

Structural refinements were also suggested, as several items were identified as “double-barreled”. Examples included items instructing users to “check and adjust” privacy settings or to “recognise and improve” prompts; these describe distinct skills that should be split into separate questions. Similarly, items requiring respondents to “distinguish who is responsible and explain why” were described as overly “chunky,” and reviewers recommended removing the additional explanatory component. Redundant pairings such as “true and trustworthy,” “write or reply,” and “use and talk” were considered unnecessary; selecting the clearer of the two terms would improve precision. Some items were also seen as too lengthy or dense. For example, reviewers suggested omitting introductory phrases such as “to recognise” in items concerning the acceptance or rejection of AI content.

Experts further identified ambiguity in several questions, where the intent or meaning was unclear. Phrases such as “so I do not have problems” prompted confusion about the type of problems the item referred to.

Others, such as “fair or unfair mistakes,” “programme an AI,” or “safe to use,” lacked specificity, making it difficult for respondents to interpret what each item measured. Similarly, broad terms like

“projects and applications” required concrete examples to avoid misinterpretation. Clarifying these concepts would reduce uncertainty and increase response accuracy.

Concrete examples and contextual supports were recommended to make items more relatable and comprehensible. Reviewers suggested adding examples, such as “Siri,” to clarify the term “voice assistant” and providing examples of social or environmental problems referenced in certain items. They also recommended simplifying activities, such as replacing “creative writing or storytelling” with “write stories,” and rethinking items that asked respondents to search for “real examples” of AI’s impact, as reviewers questioned whether youth would realistically engage in such tasks.

Consistency in terminology and formatting was another area for improvement. Experts noted the interchangeability of terms such as AI tool, AI system, and AI app and recommended that the scale adopt a single, consistent label. They also suggested reorganising the question order by placing more advanced skills, such as programming or developing AI tools, toward the end of the scale to avoid overwhelming less-experienced users. Additionally, reviewers expressed concern that technical terminology, particularly regarding privacy settings, may not translate effectively for refugee youth, underscoring the need for clearer, more universally accessible language.

Finally, in an informal follow-up conversation, an Okan teacher reinforced these concerns, noting that one particular item would be especially difficult for students with low to medium Dutch proficiency due to its abstract wording and unclear objective. She strongly recommended avoiding abstract formulations and instead using concrete, simple language paired with visual supports. According to her, including examples such as screenshots of real AI applications (e.g., ChatGPT or Gemini) would be far more helpful than the current visuals, enabling students to grasp the intended meaning of the questions better. Together, these insights highlight clear pathways for improving clarity, accessibility, and usability across the yAILS instrument.

Potential expert bias

One of the core challenges in developing valid and context-sensitive measurement instruments, such as the Youth AI Literacy Scale (yAILS), is balancing expert feedback with direct input from the target population. The differences between the youth interview responses, as detailed in the next section, and those of the experts can be understood through the dynamics of expert bias and the distinct perspectives each group brings. Experts, drawing on extensive professional experience and well-developed mental models, often view interview questions as universally clear and relevant, relying on their background to interpret dilemmas and identify multiple layers of meaning (Walker & Larson, 2012). This can lead them, often unintentionally, to overlook how their assumptions differ from those of young people. As a result, some questions may not have aligned with their lived realities. Similarly, research by Spurava & Kotilainen found that youth are more likely to challenge conventional understandings of digital media literacy and disinformation. In contrast, experts might prioritise established frameworks, resulting in different perceptions and knowledge on these aspects (Spurava & Kotilainen, 2022). Additionally, social class biases (Spencer et al., 2021) may influence how experts perceive and engage with young people, sometimes leading to deficit-based assumptions that can further distance expert interpretations from youth perspectives (Spencer et al., 2021).

In our case, while the majority of expert reviewers affirmed the clarity and relevance of the scale items, our cognitive interviews with refugee and unaccompanied youth revealed a different reality: many items were perceived as challenging to understand, abstract, or contextually disconnected from their digital practices. This tension highlights the epistemological gap between expert knowledge and

user experience, particularly when working with vulnerable or marginalised populations whose languages, literacy levels, and everyday encounters with AI may differ significantly from mainstream or academic assumptions. Such divergence is not uncommon in instrument development. Scholars have cautioned that expert feedback can unintentionally overlook linguistic complexity, cultural mismatch, or implicit assumptions embedded in scale items (Willis, 2005; Collins, 2015). Experts often exhibit fluency bias, assuming that because a term is familiar to them, it should be equally accessible to others. This mismatch can lead to inflated assessments of clarity or to an underestimate of cognitive demands, particularly among youth populations with limited exposure to formal or abstract technological concepts.

To address this, we propose the following corrective strategies:

1. **Prioritising cognitive interview findings in item refinement:** Where discrepancies exist between expert approval and user confusion, we give greater weight to the lived comprehension of the target group.
2. **Simplifying language without diluting meaning:** We revised items flagged as difficult for syntactic simplicity, reduced jargon, and increased contextual relevance.
3. **Including representative experts:** Future expert panels should include youth educators, social workers, or NGO practitioners who work closely with the target population and may offer more grounded insights.
4. **Iterative co-designing with youth:** Future research should engage youth participants directly in item wording and testing sessions to promote genuine co-creation and increase the scale's face validity.
5. **Using dual-rater strategy:** Future analysis could combine expert scores with user ratings (via comprehension testing or response latency) to triangulate item effectiveness before large-scale validation.

Ultimately, while expert input offers important theoretical guardrails, it should not override empirical signals from the very individuals for whom the tool is designed. In youth-focused scale development, particularly with vulnerable groups, validity is not only a psychometric concern but also an ethical one, and we must ensure that the tool speaks with, rather than over, its intended users.

Conclusion

The expert review confirms the robustness of the scale, covering the main skills people need when working with AI. Experts agreed that most questions were relevant and well designed, and they offered helpful suggestions to make some of them clearer or less repetitive. However, when we talked with young people in the cognitive interviews, we discovered an important gap. Although experts thought the questions were easy to understand, many young participants said they struggled with certain words or found some questions too abstract. This difference underscores the importance of evaluating expert opinions against the lived experiences of the people for whom the tool is intended.

Cognitive Interviews

Prior exposure to AI varied considerably among the participants.

Of the six interviewed unaccompanied minors, two reported no prior knowledge of AI and were unfamiliar with the AI applications we mentioned, such as ChatGPT. Three participants reported limited familiarity with AI tools and reported some familiarity with tools such as ChatGPT or translation apps, which they primarily used to support learning Dutch or English. Only one boy, a 17-year-old from Afghanistan who also attended an Okan class, appeared familiar with AI and other digital tools, such as social media, search engines, and web browsers. He also told that he had used some AI tools such

as ChatGPT or Google Translate, as well as other (AI and non-AI driven) apps on his phone, although not frequently. During the interview, it became apparent that his command of Dutch was higher than that of the other children interviewed. This facilitated cognitive interviewing.

Overall, AI knowledge and ability to evaluate items

Across five interviews, participants demonstrated limited general knowledge of AI concepts and awareness of AI-driven tools, including smartphone apps. This, together with their limited Dutch and or English language proficiency, significantly affected their ability to evaluate many of the scale items. When participants lacked a foundational understanding of AI, they were often unable to judge whether an item was relevant or accurately worded, either because the concepts were unfamiliar to them or because the language was overly complex (e.g., long sentences, complex vocabulary, or technical jargon).

Participants with stronger English or Dutch proficiency tended to have slightly better awareness of AI, primarily because they used language-learning applications or occasionally interacted with ChatGPT. However, with the exception of one boy, these participants appeared to have a limited, task-based understanding. They did not recognise the broader presence of AI in the apps they use daily (e.g., TikTok or YouTube recommendations, translation or real-time navigation tools such as Google Translate and Google Maps). This lack of awareness is not limited to this specific population; it is consistent with broader patterns observed among youth and adults.

Clarity and comprehension of items

Participants were generally able to evaluate items when the questions were short, and the language used was simple and concrete. Items that included technical or abstract terminology were complex and, at times, impossible for some participants to comprehend.

For the English version of the scale, these problematic terms included:

Algorithm/algorithms, Frameworks, Multimodal, Fairness / fair, Evaluate / evaluation, Integrate/integration, Neutral / neutrality, Prompts, Generative

According to researcher 1, the English words were consistently flagged as unclear or unfamiliar across linguistic backgrounds.

For the Dutch version of the scale, the problematic terms included:

AI [AI / Artificial Intelligence], Betrouwbare bronnen [Reliable sources], Prompts [Prompts], Patroon [Pattern], Tool [Tool], Vooroordelen [Bias / Prejudices], Evenement organiseren [Organize an event], Milieu [Environment], Zorgt [Takes care / Provides], Samenleving [Society], Vergelijken [Compare], Meningen [Opinions], Onaardig [Unkind], Reageren [Respond / React], Dagelijkse leven [Daily life]

The Dutch terms flagged can be grouped as technical jargon (AI, prompts, patroon, betrouwbare bronnen, tool) and general language (reageren, vooroordelen, evenement organiseren, milieu, zorgt, samenleving, vergelijken, meningen, onaardig, dagelijkse leven). The latter primarily reflected the lower level of target-language proficiency of participants 4 and 5. Participant 6, whose command of the language was more advanced, was able to understand the meaning of almost all the words contained in the six questions he chose. He flagged only two technical terms he did not know (patroon, prompt) and a general term he found confusing (dagelijkse leven).

Population characteristics at Fedasil

Based on these interviews, the youth population at the centre appears to be heterogeneous linguistically and in terms of their digital/AI skills. AI understanding appears to be slightly better when individuals know or are learning a second language (other than their mother tongue), which influences both whether they use AI tools and how they discuss them. Often, these participants use applications that are AI-driven, but they do not recognise AI operating behind the scenes, which limits their ability to meaningfully engage with some knowledge-based items.

Items tested

In total, 15 items were tested in English, including nine skill items and six knowledge items. A complete overview of the corresponding sentences linked with these codes can be found in Table 2.

The items checked included:

- Skill items: S17, S23, S15, S14, S28, S27, S21, S23, S6
- Knowledge items: K1, K24, K16, K4, K5, K24

Also, 16 items were tested in Dutch: eight skills and eight knowledge items. Item K5 was tested twice:

- Skill items: S3, S4, S8, S10, S17, S18, S19, S29
- Knowledge items: K3, K5 (x2), K7, K11, K17, K20, K21, K29

On the next page, an overview of all checked items in Table 2 is provided.

Table 2: Overview of checked items

Code	Item Text
S3	I know how to improve the answers I get from an AI tool by changing or refining my prompts or questions.
S4	I know how to choose the most suitable AI tool or app for what I want to do.
S6	I know how to use AI tools to make my work or study tasks more efficient.
S8	I know how to check whether information created or suggested by AI is true and trustworthy.
S10	I know how to verify AI-generated information by evaluating its accuracy and checking it against credible sources.
S14	I know how to design and develop projects or applications that use AI tools.
S15	I know how to select useful tools (e.g., frameworks, programming languages) to program an AI.
S17	I know how to use AI to create a poster for an event I am organizing.
S18	I know how to use AI (e.g., Gemini or ChatGPT) to make a social media post gain more attention.
S19	I know how to ask clear and specific questions when I use an AI chatbot so I get helpful answers.
S21	I know how to work with an AI tool to plan or create something together, such as a story, design, or project.
S23	I know how to recognize when AI tools don't think or feel like people when I talk or write to them.
S27	I know how to double-check answers from an AI tool (e.g., ChatGPT) using trusted sources to see if they are correct and safe to use.
S28	I know how avoid sharing personal details when using an AI tool to keep my information safe.
S29	I know how to find real examples of how AI has changed people's jobs, environment, education, or daily life.
K1	AI systems follow rules made by people and a combination of math and logic to make choices.
K3	Tools like ChatGPT make new things by finding patterns in data, but they don't really understand what they say.
K4	AI can think and make its own choices without help from people.
K5	AI always works perfectly, and it cannot make mistakes.
K7	The answers given by AI tools are always correct, so there is no need to double-check them.
K11	AI tools are completely free from human bias.
K16	AI can create completely original content, without using existing information.
K17	Using AI tools to do homework or assignments is the same as doing it myself.
K20	AI tools can influence the opinions I see online.
K21	An AI app may respond unpleasantly to my prompts.
K24	There is no risk in getting emotional support from an AI.
K29	AI tools never cause any social or environmental problems.

Item comprehension analysis based on participant feedback

How participants categorised the difficulty of the items during the cognitive interviews is reflected in the sub-sections below (Table 3).

1. Items considered difficult to explain

(Participants understood the general idea but could not articulate or paraphrase it)

- **Items in English:** S17, K24, S23, S15, S28, S27, K2

These items were cognitively demanding although participants could grasp part of the meaning, they struggled to explain the concept, give examples, or clarify what the item was asking. This suggests abstract wording, layered ideas, or unfamiliar terminology.

- **Items in Dutch:** K3, K29, S17
 - **K3:** In this item the term “patroon” was identified as difficult. Although the participant claimed to understand the question, it remained unclear for Researcher 2 if this was really the case due to difficulties to rephrase the question and to give concrete examples to illustrate item comprehension.

In a later conversation with an Okan teacher, this item was flagged as very confusing and abstract for students from Okan class. The recommended simplifying the item, avoiding as much as possible abstract terms and using basic, everyday language and shorter sentences.

- **K29:** Apart from having difficulties to grasp the meaning of specific terms such as “zorgt” [causes] and “milieu” [environment], the participant did not seem to grasp the question. This was probably due to a lack of awareness about the impact of AI on the environment.
- **S17:** In this item, the terms “een evenement organiseren” [organise an event] were unknown. The supervisor suggested modifying this example by “een feestje maken” [have a party]. After the clarification, and despite understanding the meanings of most individual words in this item, the question remained difficult.

2. Items not understood at all

(Participants indicated they did not understand the meaning of the item.)

- **Items in English:** K1, S23, S6

These items exceed the participants’ current knowledge of AI or use terminology that is too technical for this age/language group. These items may require simplification, additional context, or example-based framing.

- **Items in Dutch:** K11, K20, S4, S10, S18, S29
 - **K11:** The term “voorordelen” (bias) was unknown to the participant, and it was difficult to explain in simple, concrete terms. Researcher 2 got the impression that despite her explanation, the item was not understood.
 - **K20** despite understanding the meaning of most words in the question, except “meningen” (opinions), the participant was unable to grasp the meaning of the question.

- **S4:** In this item the terms “App” and “AI” caused difficulties and got somehow confused with each other. It is unclear if this confusion stems from the participant’s little familiarity with AI and/or to the low Dutch proficiency level of the participant.
- **S10:** The participant indicated that he was not sure if he understood the question, even after explaining the meaning of the terms that were flagged as difficult, namely “betrouwbare bronnen” [reliable sources] and “vergelijken” [compare].
- **S18:** Although the participant with the highest command of Dutch mentioned that this item was clear to him, Researcher 2 got the impression that the participant was using his previous knowledge of social media platforms to answer the questions (e.g. he knew how to get likes on a post). During the conversation with the researcher, it was not evident that the participant grasped if nor how AI impacts social media.

S29: In this item, the term “dagelijkse leven” [daily life] was flagged as difficult. The rest of the terms were familiar to the participant with the highest command of Dutch. Despite understanding the words, the item proved complex and too abstract. It was not clear for the participant what the aim of the question was.

3. Items easy to understand

(Participants could clearly explain the item and felt confident answering)

- **Items in English:** K16, K1, S4, K4, K5, K24, S21

These items were generally short, concrete, and written in plain language. Note: K1 and K24 appear in multiple categories, suggesting inconsistent comprehension across participants, possibly due to differences in English proficiency or background knowledge. This may indicate the need to refine clarity or provide clearer examples.

- **Items in Dutch:** K5, K7, K17
 - **K5:** In terms of vocabulary, the question was easy to understand by the participant with the highest Dutch proficiency level. However, another participant who tested the same question was unable to understand the question without additional help. Given that most of the words in the item were known to both participants and the question was short, the level of difficulty for the second participant may stem from either his lack of familiarity with AI and/or his lower Dutch proficiency level.
 - **K7:** The participant indicated that this question was easy to understand.
 - **K17:** The participant indicated that this was an “OK” question, simple and not too long

4. Items with irrelevant or confusing images

(The visual did not match or support the meaning of the item)

- **Items in English:** S15

Two participants indicated that the accompanying image did not help them interpret the item and may have caused confusion. The visual needs revision to better reflect the intended meaning or should be removed.

- **Items in Dutch:** Not observed. No comments were made regarding the visuals.

5. Items understandable in general, but with difficult words

(Participants understood the sentence overall but flagged specific terms as unclear)

- **Items in English:** S14, S20

These items contain technical or academic English vocabulary that challenged participants (e.g., “integrate,” “evaluate,” “fairness,” “prompts”, “tools”, etc.). Simplifying the language or providing examples may improve comprehension.

- **Items in Dutch:** K21, S3K21: In this item, terms difficult to understand were “reageren” [react] and “onaardig” [unpleasant]. The Centre supervisor suggested changing this term by “lief”. Despite clarifying these terms, the item remained difficult to understand, which suggests limited knowledge of AI among the participant.
- **S3:** In this item, the term “prompts” was flagged as unknown. The wording of the question should be simplified (e.g., provide a concrete example, such as ChatGPT or Gemini, instead of “an AI tool”), and the item should be shortened.

6. Items flagged as too long

(Length of the item made it harder to follow)

- **Items in English:** S27

This item’s length contributed to difficulty, especially for young people with lower literacy levels. Shortening the item or breaking it into simpler parts may enhance clarity.

- **Items in Dutch:** S8, S19
 - **S8:** This item was identified as too long and, apparently, it was a bit difficult to grasp.
 - **S19:** The question was perceived as too long and difficult to grasp. These terms flagged as difficult: “inhoud” [content], tools and “aanpassen” [modify]

Overall interpretation

- **Items that were short, concrete, and written in plain language tended to be understood better.**
- **Items containing technical vocabulary, abstract concepts, or lengthy phrasing generated the most difficulty.**
- **Inconsistent classification across participants for certain items (e.g., K1, K24) indicates that language proficiency plays a major role in comprehension.**
- **Visual support needs careful alignment with item concepts to avoid confusion.**

Table 3: Overview of cognitive interview results

Category	Definition	Items Reported by Participants (English version)	Items Reported by Participants (Dutch version)	Interpretation/ Implications
Difficult to explain	Participant understands the general idea but cannot explain it, paraphrase it, or give examples.	S17, K24, S23, S15, S28, S27, K2	K3, K29, S17	Items may contain abstract or multi-layered concepts; wording may require simplification or added examples.
Not understood at all	Participant cannot interpret the meaning of the item.	K1, S23, S6	K11, K20, S4, S10, S18, S29	Items likely contain unfamiliar technical concepts; require substantial simplification or reframing.
Easy to understand	Participant clearly understands the meaning and can explain it confidently.	K16, K1, S4, K4, K5, K24, S21	K5, K7, K17	Items use simple, concrete language. Note: K1 and K24 show inconsistent understanding across participants—consider clarifying wording.
Image not relevant/ confusing	The visual does not match or support the meaning of the item.	S15	n/a	Replace or revise image to align with item concept; irrelevant visuals create confusion.
Understandable but contains difficult words	Participant grasps the main idea but flags specific vocabulary as unclear.	S14, S20	K21, S3	Replace difficult terminology (e.g., integrate, evaluate, fairness) with simpler alternatives.
Too long/ overly complex	Participant reports the item is difficult to follow due to length.	S27	S8, S19	Shorten item and simplify structure; break into smaller parts if needed.

Conclusions

These findings will guide refinement of item wording particularly simplifying terminology, increasing contextual examples, and assessing whether certain items require scaffolding or restructuring before formal translation and broader testing.

- Most items tested in both languages were difficult for participants to understand.
- Because participants were allowed to choose which questions to test, it became clear that many items were perceived as (too) long and were therefore immediately excluded. This should be considered when interpreting the table above, which does not flag many Dutch items as lengthy.
- Target-language proficiency appears to play a crucial role in participants' comprehension of the questions. Higher proficiency is associated with a greater likelihood of understanding the intended meaning.
- Items referring to social media require particular attention. Respondents tended to conflate AI with social media, often drawing on their prior social-media knowledge and skills rather than their AI-related skills when providing answers.

Pilot survey testing

To develop and validate the scale, the research team conducted a series of *exploratory factor analyses (EFAs)* using survey data from approximately 1,200 young people in Belgium using the initially developed scale. To assess the stability of the results, the dataset was randomly split into two groups of 600 participants each, and the analysis was repeated on both subsamples. A third EFA was then conducted using the full dataset.

Before running these analyses, several standard checks confirmed that the data were appropriate for this type of statistical modelling. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure showed that the sample size was adequate, and Bartlett's test of sphericity indicated that the items were suitably correlated ($p < .001$). The team used principal axis factoring with oblimin rotation, which allows the identified factors to be related to one another. Factors were retained when their eigenvalues exceeded 1, in accordance with widely used criteria.

Because AI literacy is a still developing concept, the team used a fully exploratory approach. At this stage, the priority was to discover which underlying dimensions naturally emerged from the data, rather than to test a pre-defined structure. For this reason, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) has not yet been conducted. This means that the stability of the factor structure in completely new samples remains to be formally tested.

To partially address this limitation, the team strengthened the internal reliability of the findings by repeating the EFA on two split samples and then on the full sample. This internal replication increases confidence in the robustness of the four-factor solution. Nevertheless, future studies, ideally using new participant groups or longitudinal data, should conduct CFA or similar techniques to confirm and refine the factor structure. This step will be taken in the next phase of the PRODIGI project. EFA on the first half ($n=600$) produced a four-factor solution (accounting for 59.8% of the variance).

Results from split sample 1

The first exploratory factor analysis (EFA) conducted on split sample 1 yielded a four-factor solution, which served as the refined model for the youth developed scale. Items were broadly clustered into

four interpretable components. This four-factor solution was selected because it offered the most interpretable and parsimonious structure with acceptable/simple loading patterns and theoretical coherence. However, the structure still showed some cross-loadings typical of an initial EFA, with some expected cross-loadings due to the oblimin rotation, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Factor loadings (Split sample 1)

	Factors			
	1	2	3	4
AITECH1	.159	-.089	-.009	.757
AITECH2	.009	-.017	.013	.874
AITECH3	.098	-.023	.017	.806
AITECH4	.081	.238	.000	.547
AITECH5	-.120	.240	-.402	.249
AITECH6	.195	.010	-.148	.525
AIINF1	.068	.122	-.282	.447
AIINF2	-.029	.039	-.624	.279
AIINF3	.086	.008	-.655	.089
AIINF4	.077	-.122	-.752	.140
AIINF5	.172	-.119	-.623	.195
AIINF6	.116	-.165	-.602	.301
AICREA1	.654	.091	.104	.192
AICREA2	.125	.707	.078	.029
AICREA3	.027	.755	.001	.012
AICREA4	.324	.128	-.297	.127
AICREA5	.539	.229	.055	.129
AICREA6	.188	.621	-.006	.032
AICOM1	.561	-.026	-.119	.231
AICOM2	.449	.010	-.335	.118
AICOM3	.776	.129	-.056	.026
AICOM4	.614	.242	-.007	.076
AICOM5	.553	-.192	-.164	.073
AICOM6	.649	-.014	-.150	.094
AIETH1	.071	.417	-.381	.092
AIETH2	-.014	.522	-.479	.020
AIETH3	.271	.020	-.738	-.163
AIETH4	-.070	.254	-.666	-.031
AIETH5	.193	.142	-.475	-.023
AIETH6	-.148	.557	-.444	.022

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.
 Rotation Method: Oblimin with Kaiser Normalization.
 Total variance explained: 59.78

- a. Rotation converged in 15 iterations.
- b. Sample adequacy: KMO = .951
- c. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: $\chi^2(df = 435) = 7876.972, p .001$

Factor 1: Content Creation + Communication

Strong positive loadings on both content creation and communication items define factor 1. Several creative-production items load highly on this factor (e.g., AICREA1, AICREA5), and this pattern is reinforced by consistently high loadings from the communication items (e.g., AICOM1, AICOM3, AICOM4, AICOM6). This factor thus represents a combined competence domain in which creative ideation, content generation, and effective articulation or prompting are integrated.

Factor 2: Ethics

Substantial positive loadings from multiple ethical items anchor factor 2. Several ethics items load strongly on this dimension (e.g., AIETH1, AIETH2, AIETH6), indicating that this factor reflects a coherent ethical judgment domain. A few creative items (e.g., AICREA2, AICREA3, AICREA6) also show moderate loadings, suggesting that creativity and ethical reflection are not fully independent in this sample. However, the core of this factor is clearly ethical competence.

Factor 3: Information Evaluation

Factor 3 is characterised by strong negative loadings from all information-evaluation items (AIINF2–AIINF6), with AIINF1 also contributing more moderately. The consistent pattern of negative loadings indicates a well-defined latent dimension representing information literacy and evaluation skills, particularly the ability to assess the trustworthiness, detect bias, and evaluate the reliability of AI outputs. Although a few items from other domains exhibit slight cross-loadings, the information items dominate this factor.

Factor 4: Technical/Operational Skills

Factor 4 is primarily defined by high loadings from the technical/operational items (AITECH1–AITECH6). Most technical items load strongly and cleanly (e.g., AITECH1, AITECH2, AITECH3), indicating that operational skills form a distinct dimension in this subsample. Some items from other domains show small cross-loadings, but the technical items clearly anchor this factor.

Results from split sample 2

An independent EFA on the second half (n=600) replicated a similar four-factor structure, indicating internal consistency across subsamples.

The exploratory factor analysis on the second subsample also produced a four-factor solution. While minor cross-loadings were present, as expected in oblique rotations, the resulting factors were clearly interpretable and showed coherent internal structure. An overview of these loadings can be found in Table 5 on the next page.

Table 5: Factor loadings (Split sample 2)

	Factors			
	1	2	3	4
AITECH1	.443	-.022	.491	.246
AITECH2	.395	-.004	.547	.275
AITECH3	.432	.075	.483	.230
AITECH4	.249	.299	.451	.180
AITECH5	-.166	.358	.533	-.082
AITECH6	.434	-.015	.539	.188
AIINF1	.136	.165	.630	.081
AIINF2	-.057	.042	.763	-.165
AIINF3	-.082	.054	.744	-.207
AIINF4	.024	-.120	.807	-.142
AIINF5	.182	-.097	.728	-.082
AIINF6	.164	-.038	.731	-.044
AICREA1	.775	.113	-.030	-.010
AICREA2	.100	.819	.013	.042
AICREA3	-.018	.811	.009	-.080
AICREA4	.341	.194	.196	-.155
AICREA5	.758	.172	-.082	-.024
AICREA6	.356	.495	-.056	-.068
AICOM1	.764	.049	.127	-.020
AICOM2	.503	.054	.271	-.098
AICOM3	.760	.069	.020	-.126
AICOM4	.754	.083	-.007	-.064
AICOM5	.623	-.217	.103	-.065
AICOM6	.655	.084	.103	-.076
AIETH1	.247	.328	.068	-.402
AIETH2	.166	.438	.080	-.433
AIETH3	.268	-.053	.298	-.537
AIETH4	.077	.166	.224	-.505
AIETH5	.329	.016	.128	-.484
AIETH6	.022	.432	.102	-.456
Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.				
Rotation Method: Oblimin with Kaiser Normalization.				
Total variance explained: 62.54				
a. Rotation converged in 21 iterations. b. Sample adequacy: KMO = .956 c. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: $\chi^2(df = 435) = 8650.826, p .001$				

Factor 1: Content Creation + Communication

Factor 1 is defined by consistently high loadings from both creative-production and communication-oriented items. Several creative items show strong associations (e.g., AICREA1, AICREA5), alongside communication items that load robustly on this factor (AICOM1, AICOM3, AICOM4, AICOM6). This pattern indicates that, for respondents, generative creativity and practical expression or prompting form a unified competence domain.

Factor 2: Content Creation + Ethics blend

Factor 2 is primarily anchored by additional creative items, particularly AICREA2 and AICREA3, which load strongly on this dimension.

Ethical items also contribute moderately (e.g., AIETH1, AIETH2, AIETH6), suggesting that some aspects of responsible creation are conceptually integrated with creative skills. This factor, therefore, reflects a secondary creative dimension with an ethical component, indicating that respondents tend to associate generative work with considerations of fairness and responsibility.

Factor 3: Information Evaluation + Technical

Factor 3 shows a clear concentration of information-evaluation items, with all AIINF items loading strongly and consistently on this factor (e.g., AIINF2-AIINF6). Notably, the technical/operational items (AITECH1-AITECH6) also load substantially on this same dimension. This indicates that information-seeking, verification, and assessment skills are closely connected to operational or tool-handling skills in this subsample. Rather than forming separate domains, these abilities appear to constitute a broader “information-technical” competence cluster.

Factor 4: Ethics

Factor 4 is characterised by strong primary loadings from all ethical items (AIETH1-AIETH6), which consistently load most strongly on this dimension. Although there are small cross-loadings elsewhere, the ethical items are clearly anchored in this factor. This suggests that ethical judgment regarding fairness, bias, and trustworthy use of AI constitutes a distinct underlying dimension in this subsample.

Results from the combined sample

The **combined-sample EFA** (N=1200) confirmed the four-factor model. With the larger sample size, item loadings stabilised and revealed four interpretable competence dimensions. An overview of these factor loadings is available in table 6 on the following page.

Table 6: Factor loadings (full sample)

	Factors			
	1	2	3	4
AITECH1	.352	-.042	-.539	.325
AITECH2	.272	.005	-.592	.358
AITECH3	.344	.040	-.518	.318
AITECH4	.183	.288	-.435	.252
AITECH5	-.142	.328	-.536	-.040
AITECH6	.357	-.008	-.520	.197
AIINF1	.116	.155	-.611	.113
AIINF2	-.037	.066	-.771	-.117
AIINF3	-.038	.065	-.726	-.158
AIINF4	.017	-.094	-.819	-.139
AIINF5	.145	-.083	-.744	-.067
AIINF6	.135	-.079	-.763	-.031
AICREA1	.783	.091	.051	.067
AICREA2	.079	.785	.035	.079
AICREA3	-.035	.829	.002	.006
AICREA4	.359	.184	-.240	-.087
AICREA5	.700	.195	.074	.032
AICREA6	.266	.577	.040	-.008
AICOM1	.734	.003	-.144	.026
AICOM2	.515	.032	-.285	-.075
AICOM3	.822	.088	.020	-.059
AICOM4	.728	.150	.023	-.007
AICOM5	.649	-.218	-.098	-.053
AICOM6	.704	.030	-.096	-.033
AIETH1	.248	.396	-.152	-.290
AIETH2	.150	.513	-.174	-.340
AIETH3	.314	.008	-.361	-.457
AIETH4	.052	.253	-.341	-.408
AIETH5	.346	.101	-.191	-.363
AIETH6	.003	.538	-.181	-.337
Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.				
Rotation Method: Oblimin with Kaiser Normalization.				
Total variance explained: 60.82%				
a. Rotation converged in 36 iterations.				
b. Sample adequacy: KMO = .963				
c. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: $\chi^2(df = 435) = 16187.942, p .001$				

Factor 1: Content Creation + Communication

Factor 1 is dominated by strong loadings from both creative-production and communication items. Creative items (e.g., AICREA1, AICREA5) load highly, and communication items (e.g., AICOM1, AICOM3, AICOM4, AICOM6) also load consistently and prominently on this factor. This pattern indicates a combined competence domain that integrates creative ideation, content generation, and expressive or prompt-formulation skills.

Factor 2: Content Creation + Ethics blend

Factor 2 is driven primarily by additional creative items, especially AICREA2, AICREA3, and AICREA6, which load strongly on this dimension. Several ethics items (e.g., AIETH1, AIETH2, AIETH6) exhibit moderate loadings, suggesting that some respondents associate the use of creative AI with ethical awareness. The factor, therefore, reflects a blended creative-ethical dimension, with creativity as the dominant component and ethics as the secondary component.

Factor 3: Information Evaluation + Technical/Operational

Factor 3 is anchored by the strongest and most consistent negative loadings across all information-evaluation items (AIINF1-AIINF6). In addition, the technical/operational items (AITECH1-AITECH6) also load substantially on this factor. This indicates that, in the full sample, operational skills and information-evaluation skills form a unified competence domain. The factor reflects the combined ability to use AI tools effectively and to assess their outputs critically.

Factor 4: Ethics (Selective)

Factor 4 is characterised by two ethics items with substantial loadings: AIETH3 (.457) and AIETH4 (.408), which anchor this dimension. The remaining ethics items load moderately but remain below the conventional .40 threshold. No items from the creative, communication, information, or technical domains load meaningfully on this factor. The pattern, therefore, indicates a narrower ethical dimension, defined most clearly by items related to fairness, bias, and responsible judgment, while other ethics items contribute only modestly.

Four Hybrid Competence Clusters

Across all three exploratory factor analyses, a consistent pattern emerged: the survey items did not group into the original, separate conceptual categories. Instead, the analyses revealed four hybrid clusters of AI competence, indicating that young people naturally associate specific skills with their own abilities. Although the strength of individual item loadings varied slightly across samples, the overall structure was stable and interpretable.

The **first and most consistent cluster combined content creation and communication skills**. In every analysis, items related to creative ideation, content creation, and generative problem-solving loaded together with items focused on formulating effective prompts and expressing ideas clearly to AI systems. This recurring pattern suggests that young people view “creating with AI” and “communicating with AI” as part of a single integrated skill set. For them, being creative with an AI tool is inseparable from the ability to provide clear instructions or to articulate their ideas in a way the system can understand.

A second blended cluster brought together aspects of content creation with ethical considerations.

Creative ideation items tended to load strongly on this factor, while ethical items showed moderate but consistent contributions. Although ethics did not dominate this cluster, the repeated appearance of this pairing indicates that young people connect responsible content generation, such as ensuring

originality, fairness, or avoiding biased outputs, with their broader creative practice. This reflects a form of “responsible creativity,” in which ethical awareness is integral to the production or imagination of AI-generated content.

A third recurring cluster involved the combination of information-evaluation skills and technical or operational abilities. Across all analyses, items focused on checking, verifying, or interpreting AI-generated information consistently formed a coherent group. However, these skills were closely intertwined with items related to operating AI tools or managing their settings. This suggests that young people do not clearly separate the act of evaluating AI outputs from the practical skills needed to use AI systems. Instead, they see these abilities as part of a broader, integrated information–technical competence: using AI effectively while understanding and critically assessing its outputs.

Finally, all analyses indicated a distinct cluster of ethical competence. This factor was populated primarily by items related to fairness, bias, and responsible judgment. Unlike the blended clusters, it did not mix with creative content production, communication, technical, or information skills. Although smaller and more focused, this cluster reflects a clear ethical dimension centred on moral evaluation and responsible decision-making in AI use. It sits alongside the blended Creative + Ethics cluster but represents a more independent form of ethical reflection.

Taken together, these hybrid clusters show how the nature of AI tools reshapes the structure of digital competences. Traditional digital skills frameworks, such as the Youth Digital Skills Indicator (yDSI), assumed that separate domains (communication, content creation, information literacy, and technical skills) could be clearly distinguished. In contrast, the factor analyses in this study reflect the integrated manner in which AI systems are used in practice. AI tools function not as passive instruments but as interactive agents that interpret user input, generate unpredictable responses, and influence how tasks are carried out. As a result, AI-related activities require users to combine skills simultaneously. Communication, content creation, evaluation, and ethical judgement often co-occur within the same task, producing hybrid competence patterns rather than neatly separated abilities. These findings suggest that AI literacy should be taught and assessed through realistic, scenario-based activities that mirror actual human–AI interaction. When young people work with AI, they naturally draw on multiple skill areas simultaneously. Embedding ethical thinking directly within these tasks, rather than treating ethics as a separate module, aligns with the patterns observed in the data. While older digital literacy models measured what individuals could do independently, AI literacy must measure what users can do in collaboration with AI systems. This shift helps explain why the factor analysis produced hybrid clusters and highlights the need for integrated approaches in future educational and assessment frameworks.

Alignment with EU digital policy frameworks

The PRODIGI competence clusters align well with current EU directions in digital and AI education. Both the Digital Education Action Plan (2021–2027) and the proposed AI Act emphasise the need for strong AI literacy among learners and everyday users. The OECD–European Commission AI Literacy Framework (2025) is also designed to be consistent with these policies and recognises AI literacy as an essential component of digital citizenship. Likewise, the EU’s DigComp 2.2 framework now explicitly includes the ability to use and assess “new and emerging technologies,” including AI.

The clusters identified in PRODIGI correspond naturally to the domains in DigComp. For example, the Content Creation + Communication cluster aligns with DigComp’s areas of Communication & Collaboration and Digital Content Creation. In contrast, the Information Evaluation + Ethics cluster corresponds to DigComp’s domains of Information & Data Literacy and Safety. In this sense, the hybrid clusters incorporate the analytical, creative, and ethical dimensions that EU frameworks expect of digitally competent citizens.

By integrating creative, informational, and ethical competencies, the AI literacy scale is well-positioned to support the EU’s goal of empowering learners in AI and to align with the AI Act’s emphasis on the responsible use of AI.

AI knowledge dimension: Understanding foundational concepts among youth

To understand how well young people grasp the basic concepts behind artificial intelligence, the study included 30 knowledge questions. These questions covered essential topics, including how AI systems work, where their data comes from, the limits of their accuracy, basic principles of machine learning, issues related to data privacy, and common misconceptions about generative models. Together, these items assessed the knowledge component of AI literacy and provided insight into young people’s understanding of how AI operates and what risks it may pose.

The responses from all 1,200 participants offer a detailed view of which concepts are familiar to young people, which are only partially understood, and where widespread misunderstandings remain. Presenting these results helps identify areas of conceptual strength and gaps that may require attention in future educational efforts. This allows educators and policymakers to address not only what young people can do with AI tools, but also what they know about the systems behind them.

Overall performance showed substantial variation. Nearly half of the respondents (48.5%) answered 16 or fewer of the 30 questions correctly. Scores ranged from 0 correct answers (6 participants) to 27 correct answers (6 participants), indicating substantial variation in conceptual understanding. A visualisation of the distribution of correct choices is provided in Figure 1, and a complete overview is provided in Appendix C.

Figure 1: visualisation of the distribution of correct choices

Age was not a significant predictor of performance on the AI knowledge scale. Participants aged 13 to 19, including the majority (84% of the sample) aged 16 and 17, showed comparable levels of AI knowledge, making it unsurprising that age did not explain variation in scores. Gender differences were also minimal: boys, girls, and non-binary youth performed similarly, although girls scored slightly higher on average (17 correct answers out of 30) compared to boys (14 correct answers).

These findings indicate that demographic characteristics do not meaningfully shape AI knowledge levels among young people. Instead, substantial differences emerged across educational tracks. Students in the **academic track** achieved the highest scores, with an average of 17 correct responses, compared with 13 for students in the dual-track programme and 11 for those in the **vocational track** ($df = 67.458, p < .001$). This clear gradient suggests that **differences in AI knowledge are strongly associated with educational pathways rather than with age or gender**. Overall, the results point to broader inequalities in learning opportunities, exposure, and access to reliable information about AI across educational contexts, rather than demographic differences within the youth population.

2. Portuguese context

Expert consultation & cognitive interviews

Clarity of language and terminology

Both experts and students noted that **several terms used in the scale were confusing or too advanced, showing that the language needs to be simplified for young audiences**. Some items included technical vocabulary that many students had never heard before. For example, one question asked about choosing AI programming tools and used the word “*frameworks*,” which students did not recognise; during testing, one student openly said that this term was unfamiliar, prompting reviewers to recommend replacing it with more common language. Another item referred to “*multimodal prompting*,” meaning giving an AI both text and images. Experts predicted that most young people would not know this term and advised explaining the idea in plain language instead. As a result, the item was rewritten to describe the concept clearly without relying on technical jargon.

Key terms used to assess AI literacy often needed more precise and more accessible wording. For example, the Portuguese words meaning “reliable” and “trustworthy” in items about evaluating AI information were considered difficult for many students, and experts noted that these terms would need explanation to ensure understanding. The concept of “bias” also caused confusion; both experts and students noted that the term used for “bias” was unfamiliar. In one knowledge item stating that AI tools are free from human bias, students did not understand the term, leading to a suggestion to replace it with a more familiar expression, such as “*human prejudices*.” Using age-appropriate language or adding short explanations helps ensure that students can follow what the items are asking.

Long or abstract sentences needed to be simplified to make them easier to understand. One skill item asked whether students knew how to improve AI answers by refining their prompts, but the verb meaning “*refine*” confused several students. Experts confirmed that some learners had never encountered the term, so the item was changed to include a simpler verb meaning “*change*” alongside “*refine*,” making the action clearer. This type of adjustment, where a complex word is paired with a more familiar one, helped students better understand what the question was asking.

Some items were also revised to include *clearer explanations or concrete examples when the original wording felt too abstract*. A knowledge item explaining that AI can produce answers without understanding them was rewritten to clearly state that the AI “*automatically creates new things but does not understand what those things mean,*” which students found easier to interpret. Another example involved the term “*deepfake.*” When students were asked about creating a deepfake, many did not know the word and misinterpreted the item. This showed the need to either define the term directly in the question or use a simple description such as “*a fake video of someone.*”

Overall, the co-design feedback supported simplifying language across the scale. Technical terms were replaced or clarified, abstract phrases were made more concrete, and the wording was aligned with students’ everyday vocabulary. Both experts and youth testers agreed that clear and plain language helps ensure the scale accurately reflects young people’s understanding of AI.

Age-appropriateness of content

The cognitive testing showed that some items, although relevant to AI literacy, were not entirely age-appropriate for younger students, given their typical knowledge and experience. One issue was that *certain questions assumed skills that many students have not yet developed*. For example, an item asking students to choose the right tools to program an AI referred to programming frameworks and languages. Reviewers noted that many students at this level do not have programming experience, and only a small number with extracurricular exposure, such as robotics or coding clubs, would understand what “*frameworks*” or programming an AI involves. This mismatch indicated that the item was too technical for most learners. As a result, reviewers recommended either removing these types of questions or reserving them for older students who have already been introduced to basic programming.

Some items relied on digital literacy concepts that students often encounter later in their schooling.

A clear example was the question about using AI in schoolwork “*while respecting originality and avoiding plagiarism.*” Experts pointed out that many students do not yet know what plagiarism means, a finding supported during cognitive interviews, where several students misunderstood the term. The item was rewritten to use more relatable language, such as “*not just copy-pasting*” someone else’s work, making the idea easier for students to understand. This revision acknowledges that expecting young learners to understand academic integrity without prior instruction is unrealistic. Future items will either include simple explanations of unfamiliar terms or use wording that reflects ideas students are more likely to know.

Questions requiring higher-level ethical reasoning also proved challenging for this age group. One item asked students to decide who should take responsibility if an AI system causes a problem. Because this situation is abstract, students struggled to interpret it without context. Experts recommended adding concrete examples, such as a self-driving car accident or an AI system giving harmful advice, to help students understand what kind of responsibility the question was referring to. A similar issue arose with an item about checking whether an AI makes “*fair or unfair mistakes.*” Students found the phrase confusing and questioned whether a mistake could be “*fair*” in any meaningful way. The item was simplified to focus on whether the AI makes mistakes at all, removing the abstract fairness distinction that students found difficult to interpret.

Another item asked students to compare how an AI behaves with “*different kinds of people*” to see if it treats everyone fairly. Experts noted that this phrasing was unclear and could even feel sensitive without further explanation. Students also struggled to understand what “*different kinds of people*” referred to. The item was revised to state more directly that students should look for situations where an AI treats some people unfairly, linking the idea to more familiar experiences of fairness and

unfairness. This more straightforward approach helps students understand what is being asked while avoiding vague or potentially uncomfortable wording.

Through these revisions, the scale now better reflects the knowledge and cognitive development of the intended age group. *Items were adapted to match what students are likely to know, clarified with examples where needed, and rewritten to avoid unnecessary technical or abstract language*, ensuring that students can meaningfully engage with the questions based on their own experiences rather than struggle with unfamiliar concepts.

Relevance to youths' experience and digital practices

Ensuring that each item connects to students' real experiences is important for both engagement and the accuracy of their responses. Cognitive testing showed *apparent differences between items that students immediately related to and those that felt distant from their everyday lives*. Many of the competency items reflected situations students commonly encounter, such as using voice assistants or tools like ChatGPT to complete tasks, creating a poster with AI, or improving a social media post. These activities match how teens already use technology, so the items were easy for them to understand. For instance, the idea of using AI to make an Instagram post more appealing resonated strongly with students. Because these scenarios were familiar, students had no trouble interpreting the questions and offering accurate answers.

Some items were rather familiar but not for all students. For example, checking whether information from an AI is correct by comparing it with other sources is something students are expected to do, although not everyone has done it in practice. Those who had already used AI tools for homework understood the need to verify information, while others needed a moment to imagine the situation. The concept became clearer once the language was adjusted to something more relatable, such as "sources you trust." Writing clear questions for an AI was also understandable, especially given how common chatbots have become, though experts noted that this item overlapped with another one and could be refined or contextualized to avoid repetition. Items in this middle range were generally workable once minor adjustments were made.

A smaller group of items felt disconnected from students' real-life experiences because they involved topics or tasks they rarely encounter. For instance, asking students to find real examples of AI's effects on jobs, the environment, or daily life felt more like a research task than a typical activity. While the idea is relevant to understanding AI's impact, it is not something students typically do outside of school assignments. Similarly, an item about the environmental impact of AI was unfamiliar to most students. Concepts like the energy footprint of AI systems were difficult for them to grasp until the phrasing was simplified. When items touched on issues students had not yet learned about, the team evaluated whether they should be revised with clearer context or replaced with examples more connected to students' digital routines.

Some attitudinal items also needed clearer grounding in students' experiences. One question suggested that speaking politely to AI tools helps avoid problems, but students did not understand what problems this referred to, since being rude to Siri or ChatGPT has no obvious consequences in their experience. Including an example or a clearer explanation made the intended message easier to grasp. Another item stated that *"There is no risk in getting emotional support from an AI,"* which students understood literally and could misinterpret. Rewriting it to *"There is risk in getting emotional support from an AI"* made the message clearer and avoided confusion caused by the original structure. These adjustments showed that even when an item covers a relevant topic, it must be framed in a way that makes sense to students' daily lives.

Overall, aligning the scale's content with students' actual experiences (such as technology use, schoolwork, and social interactions) helps ensure that the measure captures what it intends to assess. Students respond more accurately when they recognize the situations described. The cognitive testing phase was essential for revealing when an item did not fit naturally with students' experiences, allowing the design team to update wording, examples, or context to improve relevance and comprehension.

Redundancy and overlap in items

The expert review also identified several items in the draft scale that repeated the same ideas or overlapped in what they measured. Redundancy can make a questionnaire feel longer than necessary and reduce the usefulness of the results, so one aim of the co-design process was to streamline the list of questions. In some cases, two items placed in different sections were essentially asking about the same skill. For example, one question about asking clear, specific questions when using an AI chatbot was almost identical to another question about writing clear prompts for AI. Because both targeted the same ability, keeping both would add little value. The plan is to retain the clearer, more general version and remove the duplicate.

A similar pattern appeared in questions about verifying information produced by AI tools. Several items asked students to confirm that AI information was accurate or trustworthy, and experts noted that these items did not differ in meaningful ways. One question concerned assessing whether information is "true and trustworthy," while another concerned evaluating accuracy by comparing it with other sources. In yet another section, a question about double-checking AI answers repeated the same idea. Too many versions of the same concept can confuse respondents or elicit repetitive responses. The recommendation is to combine these into a single, well-phrased question about fact-checking AI outputs, unless different aspects require separate measurement, such as accuracy versus bias.

There was also a draft item that sought to measure two distinct abilities simultaneously: generating ideas for AI projects and developing those projects. Experts pointed out that these are separate skills, and some students might be comfortable coming up with ideas but not with building something technical, or vice versa. Splitting the item into two clearer questions, or rewording it to focus on just one task, will give more precise information and make it easier for students to respond.

Although concerns about redundancy mainly came from experts, student feedback supported this point as well. During testing, a few students commented that some items felt repetitive, or they referred back to an earlier answer when a similar question appeared. This suggests that students do notice overlap, even if they do not always express it directly. Reducing repetition helps keep students engaged and makes each question feel meaningful.

Conclusions and recommendations

Cognitive testing combined with expert review proved essential in validating and improving the AI literacy scale. The co-design approach ensured that the instrument is both theoretically sound and practically accessible to the target youth audience. Based on the synthesis of findings, the following actions for finalizing the scale were recommended.

Revise wording for clarity

First, **wording should be simplified by replacing technical terms with everyday language or adding brief explanations where needed** (e.g. describing AI as computer tools that answer questions or create content, and rephrasing bias as treating some people unfairly). Items should be written in language that reflects how 12–15-year-olds speak in everyday situations. Moreover, abstract or ethical concepts should be supported with short, concrete examples to help respondents easily imagine real-life situations.

Ensure age-appropriate content

A second important finding concerns the need to remove or adapt materials that assume knowledge beyond students' age or experience. **Items requiring advanced technical or programming knowledge should be omitted or included only when students are expected to have that background.** For unfamiliar concepts such as plagiarism or deepfakes, short explanations should be added directly in the item or as a brief note (e.g. explaining plagiarism as “copy-pasting someone else’s text and saying it is your own”). Working with educators can help ensure that all concepts used in the survey are covered in the curriculum. Overall, the goal is to ensure that all students, regardless of academic track, can understand each question well enough to provide a thoughtful answer.

Increase relevance and engagement

Third, it is important to **ground items in situations that feel authentic and engaging to students.** In this regard, questions should refer to AI tools young people already know, such as chatbots, image generators, or social media recommendations. For less engaging topics, such as AI’s environmental impact, interest can be increased by presenting a short fact or using a simple true/false format. Ongoing involvement of young people in reviewing items is essential to ensure they feel relevant. If an item cannot be made relatable, it should be revised, introduced with a brief explanation, or reconsidered for inclusion.

Eliminate redundancies

Fourth, the interviews indicated the need to **consolidate survey items by merging similar questions and removing redundancies duplicates.** Each item should assess a distinct aspect of AI literacy, and the revised scale should be reviewed again to ensure no unintended overlap remains. This streamlining will shorten the survey, improve the response experience, and reduce the risk of contradictory responses due to similar questions. The resulting item set will be concise, comprehensive, and non-repetitive.

Verify again if necessary.

Finally, the interview findings **suggest conducting a second round of cognitive pre-testing or piloting after making revisions, ideally with a different group of students.** This step will confirm whether the changes have effectively addressed the issues (for example, students now understand “*tendencioso*” instead of “*enviesado*”, or they correctly handle the revised plagiarism item) and check that no new confusions have arisen.

Ongoing expert input is key to keep content aligned with the AI literacy framework’s goals and ensure its reliability and validity after updates.

In summary, the co-design process has greatly enhanced the AI literacy scale. By focusing on youth-friendly language, age-appropriate content, real-world relevance, and concise coverage of topics, the improved tool will more accurately assess students’ AI literacy levels. The integration of expert and student insights – *including their disagreements* – provided valuable guidance: areas of consensus highlighted clear priorities for change, while differences (such as assumptions made by adults versus actual student knowledge) emphasised the importance of incorporating learners’ perspectives in the design. The finalized scale, as shown in this report, embodies these collective insights. It functions as a tool that is both educationally robust and genuinely co-created with its end users, ensuring it will produce valid results during future field testing.

This analysis utilises qualitative feedback from expert reviewers of the Portuguese AI literacy scale (Comments from Portugal expert review) and annotations from cognitive testing sessions with Portuguese students (cognitive testing spreadsheet data). Key examples and quotations from these sources are cited to support the findings, such as expert notes on terminology explanations and student feedback on confusing terms or items. These combined insights informed the development of item-level recommendations, ensuring the scale's validity and its responsiveness to youth.

The initial version of the yAILS, tested through expert feedback, cognitive interviews, and the school survey, is presented in Appendix C, and the refined version is presented in Appendix D.

3. Polish Context

Expert consultation

The dynamic development of digital technologies and the rapid spread of artificial intelligence-based tools present both opportunities and new challenges for older people. Contemporary research emphasises that effective digital inclusion of older people requires not only access to technology, but also the reduction of cognitive, social and emotional barriers that prevent them from fully participating in the digital world (Tomczyk & Kielar, 2025a). In the Polish context of technological education for older adults, there is a growing need to redefine teaching models so that they respond to the rapid pace of change and the diverse levels of competence of older adults (Tomczyk & Kielar, 2025b). At the same time, studies conducted in diverse urban and rural environments show that digital exclusion is structural in nature and affects the well-being, sense of agency and opportunities for social participation of seniors (Diana et al., 2025).

In this context, diagnostic tools that allow for a reliable assessment of the digital competence of older people are of particular importance. The latest work on educational goals in the area of digital inclusion emphasises the need to simplify language, embed content in real-life situations, and adapt the pace and form to the specificities of late adulthood (Tomczyk & Edisherashvili, 2024).

The results of the qualitative part of the study presented in this report confirm this need: experts emphasise the importance of simplicity, clarity and practicality of tools, while pointing out that their excessive length and technicality can lead to cognitive overload in older people.

The study was conducted in the second half of November 2025 using in-depth, semi-structured online interviews with prominent Polish experts in the field of digital education for older adults – practitioners with many years of experience in training, consulting and academic work. The material was subjected to thematic analysis, focusing on identifying common problem areas and areas of consensus among specialists. This approach made it possible to capture both the dominant patterns of thinking about the digital competences of older people and practical guidelines for the design of diagnostic tools. By combining an empirical perspective (backed by extensive professional experience) with current knowledge in the field of andragogy and geragogy, this part of the report presents the directions for necessary modifications to the tool and indicates the principles that should shape future solutions supporting the digital inclusion of seniors in the effective use of AI or increasing resistance to manipulation and disinformation mediated by new media.

1. Positive aspects of the tool

Basic geragogical assumptions emphasise that older people learn more effectively when the content is close to their everyday experiences and does not require specialised vocabulary. Andragogy, on the other hand, indicates that adults (including seniors) need a sense of competence and comprehensibility of materials in order to enter the learning process without frustration. The respondent notes that some of the questions in the tool meet these minimum conditions: they are general, based on everyday phrases, and do not present the user with unnecessary cognitive barriers. These types of elements are a friendly starting point, consistent with adult learning theory.

"I didn't mark which questions could be left out, but I think the most general ones are still suitable. Sometimes there were more general questions, and they are still okay because they use normal, everyday phrases." (Respondent 1, female, extensive experience in training seniors)

In the process of adult education, favourable conditions are extremely important: visual comfort, clarity and aesthetics. Barriers such as a too-small font size or a chaotic layout can completely block access to the content. Respondent 2 points out that the tool has graphic qualities that can act as a facilitator, although she emphasises differences in the level of preparation across different groups of seniors, which is consistent with geragogical theory on the heterogeneity of the 60+ population.

"On the positive side, the tool is really well designed graphically. The font size is also fine. Overall, I have one thought that sums it all up: this tool is great, but for advanced users – for students. I can see that it could even be introduced for seniors in Krakow, but not for other groups."

(Respondent 2, male, extensive experience in training seniors in the use of AI)

From a geragogy perspective, it is important to eliminate elements that overload perception, and one of the most significant burdens in working with older people is an excess of material and an overly long list of questions. Respondent 3, as a practitioner of senior education, notes that although the form of the answers may be user-friendly, their potential is negated by the excessive number of tasks. Her comment points to the need to apply the principle of "less is more", which is key in teaching people in late adulthood.

"In my experience, such a number of survey questions will discourage them, even though the forms of answering are simple." (Respondent 3, female, extensive experience in senior education, university employee)

2. Negative aspects of the research tool

2a. Too difficult language and specialist vocabulary

Geragogical studies have repeatedly confirmed that seniors need the language of reality, not the language of technology, especially when learning something completely new. Exceeding the limits of comprehensibility impedes learning because, unlike younger people, older adults cannot compensate for their lack of digital intuition. Respondent 1 points out a fundamental barrier: the very word "AI" is unclear to many of them, which means that the tool needs to be thoroughly simplified before it can even be measured.

"There are names there that are closely related to artificial intelligence and tools. And, gosh, how is a senior citizen supposed to figure that out? What's more, for some seniors, even the abbreviation 'AI' will be a bit of a mystery."

(Respondent 1, female, extensive experience in training seniors)

In the next excerpt, the same person emphasises that overly difficult questions are not only a problem for seniors; even educated adults may have difficulty interpreting them. This is an important point from an andragogical perspective: a tool cannot place demands on its users that exceed their competencies.

"Can we, as adults who consciously use these tools, clearly identify which tool provides incorrect or less clear answers? I think that even for some of us, such a test would be quite interesting."

(Respondent 1, female, extensive experience in training seniors)

From a geragogy perspective, digital inequalities should be taken into account, especially between urban and rural seniors. Overly difficult language and question structure can completely exclude a significant proportion of respondents. The respondent points out that many questions are formulated

in a non-intuitive way, which contradicts the principles of adult education, which assume comprehensibility as a condition for cognitive engagement.

"Most rural seniors will not understand them, and that is my biggest hesitation. For them, the content of the questions will be too complicated, even the structure of the questions will be incomprehensible. In my opinion, is the biggest problem with this tool." (Respondent 2, male, extensive experience in training seniors in the use of AI)

In senior education, clarity is extremely important. Older people are less likely to guess meanings or contexts. The introduction of unclear or imprecise concepts, especially in English, violates the basic principles of geragogy. The respondent points to specific examples that could undermine seniors' sense of understanding and confidence.

"I have doubts — perhaps due to a lack of knowledge — about the content of certain questions and understanding the essence of the question: slide 8 = fair/unfair mistakes?; slide 9 — treats everyone fairly; slide 12 — examples of how... implied positive/negative changes?" (Respondent 3, female, extensive experience in educating seniors, university employee)

2b. Questions that are too detailed and demanding

One of the key principles of geragogy is that learning should be functional, i.e. related to everyday life practices. Overly detailed questions requiring technical knowledge not only violate this principle but can also cause competence anxiety, which blocks further cooperation. The respondent notes that some questions require an understanding of topics that most seniors have never needed to learn.

"For me, this tool is too detailed. It asks very precise questions that a senior citizen cannot answer without basic knowledge. There was something about creating emails or email accounts, and not every senior citizen is aware of this." (Respondent 1, female, extensive experience in training senior citizens)

Respondent 2 also points to a typical pattern of technology use among older people that is highly simplified, indicating that the tool does not correspond to their actual behaviour, a fundamental flaw from the perspective of senior education.

"Seniors who use email accounts have them, but do they use them consciously [...] Their use ends with them being able to log into their account, usually on one computer, because they have their password saved there." (Respondent 1, female, extensive experience in training seniors)

Basic andragogical assumptions emphasise that teaching adults must begin with learners' prior experiences. Respondent 2 points out that the questions in the tool are detached from seniors' everyday practices and therefore devoid of cognitive meaning. She points out how important it is to base questions on specific activities that are close to everyday life.

"In questions such as 'I know how to use tools to plan a project together', you have to write something specific. [...] They must have a particular task that relates to their lives, for example: 'I know how to create a recipe for chicken soup using an AI tool' or 'I know how to write wishes for my grandson'." (Respondent 2, male, extensive experience in training seniors in the use of AI)

According to the basic principles of geragogy, every educational activity must be firmly anchored in the realities of an older person's life. Pointing to school tasks or exercises familiar to young people is grossly inadequate. The respondent clearly emphasises this inconsistency:

"The final part of the survey contains questions related to education — writing homework, creating a poster. In my opinion, these can be removed, since the respondents are seniors."
(Respondent 3, female, extensive experience in educating seniors, university employee)

2c. Overload, repetitiveness, unclear logic

Excessive material is one of the major barriers to learning for older adults. This is due to natural cognitive processes and ageing. The respondent reports her personal experience of reviewing the tool, which points to its tiring and repetitive nature.

"For me, there is too much material. It is all too long. By the twelfth page, the twelfth question, when I was reviewing this PDF, I had the impression that it was always the same thing, just in different colours." (Respondent 1, female, extensive experience in training seniors)

Based on accumulated experience, the research tool should not only be simple but also methodologically reliable. Respondent 2 points out that many tools cannot fulfil their function because most seniors will not understand their content. This indicates that a complete redesign is required, not merely cosmetic changes.

"In my opinion, the entire questionnaire needs to be thoroughly redesigned. [...] In its current state, seniors will not understand the questions. Maybe they will understand one, two, three."
(Respondent 2, male, extensive experience in training seniors in the use of AI)

From the perspective of basic research methodology, the structure of educational material should be consistent, predictable and logical. The respondent points out that the tool contains duplicates and unclear distinctions, which creates an unnecessary burden for older people.

"Such a number of survey questions will discourage them. I suggest that certain questions — and there are several that sound similar — be presented as one." (Respondent 3, female, extensive experience in educating seniors, university employee)

"I am wondering about questions I.2, II.1 and III.1 in the skills section — to me, they are identical."
(Respondent 3, female, extensive experience in educating seniors, university employee)

3. Opinions on the ideal tool

In geragogy, there is a principle of prioritising short, clear materials. The more minimalist the tool, the greater the chances of engagement. The respondent indicates the optimal form: one sheet, clear and organised.

"The ideal tool would be short and clear. One sheet, printed on both sides at most."
(Respondent 1, female, extensive experience in training seniors)

Respondent 2 emphasises that the tool must limit the number of questions to an absolute minimum. According to andragogy, the less content there is, the greater the concentration and motivation of adult learners, and this effect is even more substantial in seniors.

"If we want reliable results, the fewer questions, the better. I would recommend 12-14 questions, really basic ones." (Respondent 2, male, extensive experience in training seniors in the use of AI)

Respondent 3 again draws attention to the need to reduce duplicates, which is consistent with both the geragogical postulate of transparency and the andragogical principle of cognitive efficiency.

"I suggest that certain questions, and there are several that sound similar, be presented as one." (Respondent 3, female, extensive experience in educating seniors, university employee)

4. Adapting the tool to the experiences of seniors

According to geragogy, older adults often use technology intuitively and unconsciously, without ascribing to it the status of "learning". The respondent describes the situation, noting that understanding this mechanism is crucial for designing competency tests.

"Sometimes they use elements of AI, but they do not feel that it can be classified as such [...]" (Respondent 1, female, extensive experience in training seniors)

At the same time, she emphasises that the lack of explanations from loved ones deepens the technological gap, which is consistent with the theory of social learning in older age.

"For many seniors, artificial intelligence is a complete abstraction. [...] Grandchildren and children do not explain to them what AI is because it is obvious to young people." (Respondent 1, female, extensive experience in training seniors)

From a geragogical perspective, the design of tools must be based on an assessment of the group's level of digitalisation. The respondent points out that a significant proportion of seniors, especially in rural areas, lack even basic devices, which significantly shapes the form of the tool.

"From my training in rural areas, I can see that the level is really low [...] Maybe 20% have smartphones." (Respondent 2, male, extensive experience in training seniors in the use of AI)

Respondent 3 discusses the problem of excessive diversity in the response categories. Seniors often do not notice subtle semantic differences. The multitude of options makes it difficult to make decisions.

"It would be difficult for me to distinguish between helpful, true, useful and reliable information. This can determine the answer." (Respondent 3, female, extensive experience in educating seniors, university employee)

5. Suggestions for test design

From the perspective of Respondent 1, questions rooted in the realities of seniors' lives help to break down abstraction. The respondent notes that seniors need examples that are close to their everyday decisions, not models.

"If these were simple statements or short situations that seniors could relate to, it would be easier for them to understand." (Respondent 1, female, extensive experience in training seniors)

R 1 also indicates that the scale should be as simple as possible, because too many options make it difficult to make a decision, which is confirmed by theories of declining information processing speed in late adulthood.

"The scale cannot be long, because many people will start to wonder whether they know a lot or a little less." (Respondent 1, female, extensive experience in training seniors)

Respondent 2 points out that seniors have difficulty recognising false content, which is one of the key areas of digital competence for people aged 65+. According to the principles of andragogy, questions must reflect real cognitive threats.

"Most rural seniors watch videos [...] the important question is whether they can distinguish between real and fake recordings." (Respondent 2, male, extensive experience in training seniors in the use of AI)

The statements also emphasise the need for interpersonal support – seniors often learn most effectively in the company of a supportive person, which fits in perfectly with the principles of geragogy regarding the role of the educator and carer.

"I imagine my groups and think that 30% of seniors will need an assistant to help them use the tool." (Respondent 2, male, extensive experience in training seniors in the use of AI)

Respondent 3 points out that excessive complexity in the response categories is contrary to both adult learning theory and the practice of working with seniors, for whom too many semantic nuances can lead to confusion.

"It would be difficult for me to distinguish between helpful, true, useful and reliable information." (Respondent 3, female, extensive experience in educating seniors, university employee)

Conclusions

Results from the expert review of the sAILS should be understood as an attempt to compare the practical observations of educators working with seniors with the current, empirically confirmed state of knowledge on learning in late adulthood. Contemporary research clearly indicates that effective education of older people requires consideration of three co-occurring areas: age-related cognitive changes (Zuber et al., 2019), sensory limitations typical of ageing (Germine et al., 2019) and the specific motivations of adult learners, including a strong focus on practicality and immediate usefulness of content (Lee et al., 2019). The table therefore presents a summary of how respondents (based on many years of experience) diagnose the compliance or non-compliance of diagnostic tools with regard to theoretical foundations.

Based on the literature on digital competence and technological education for older adults, it is evident that individuals aged 65 and over are particularly susceptible to information overload, difficulties in grasping abstract technological concepts, and challenges in processing complex digital messages (Grotto & Buja, 2025; Nedeljko et al., 2022). Research further emphasizes that effective digital education for this group, and the assessment of its outcomes, should adopt a geragogical approach, characterized by short learning modules, the use of plain and colloquial language, integration into everyday practices, and strong, ongoing instructional support (Gates and Wilson-Menzfeld, 2022; Lee, 2023). The respondents' comments regarding overly technical language, insufficient practical examples, and the excessive length of the tool implicitly corroborate these recommendations.

A distinct and increasingly important line of research focuses on the vulnerability of older adults to misinformation and media manipulation.

The literature suggests that this vulnerability does not stem from diminished ability, but rather from differences in cognitive processing and media socialisation compared to younger generations, which can make it more challenging for older individuals to evaluate the credibility of visual and digital content (Brashier & Schacter, 2020; Guess et al., 2019). Consequently, questions addressing AI, deepfakes, or the broader impacts of technology must be formulated in an exceptionally simple and transparent manner. Otherwise, the instrument risks capturing confusion or subjective perceptions rather than actual knowledge, which may not accurately reflect real conditions. The table below translates the empirical findings into concrete design recommendations concerning the structure, language, length, and internal logic of the diagnostic tool.

Table 7: Overview of feedback

Area/topic	Respondent 1 (F, senior training)	Respondent 2 (M, senior training in AI)	Respondent 3 (F, senior education, university)	Practical implications (geragogy/andragogy)
Positive aspects of the tool	General questions based on everyday language are understandable for seniors and can remain in the tool.	Very good aesthetics, legible font – visually, the tool is user-friendly, but rather for advanced users.	The simple form of the answers is an advantage, but is lost when there are too many questions.	Keep: good graphic design, large letters, simple language and general questions. Reduce: the number of items so that the positives "come to the fore".
Language and terminology	Overly specialised terms (AI, tools, programming languages) – seniors do not understand the terms. Even adult users of the tools have difficulty with some of the questions.	Rural seniors will not understand most of the questions – difficult wording, complex sentence structures.	Unclear English terms ("fair/unfair mistakes", "treats everyone fairly", etc.) raise doubts even among educators.	Use colloquial and unambiguous language , avoid AI jargon. In accordance with geragogy – minimise cognitive load, in accordance with andragogy – language must be transparent and understandable to the recipient.
Level of difficulty and detail of questions	The tool is too detailed and requires technical knowledge (emails, mailboxes) that seniors often do not have.	The questions are detached from the real tasks of seniors; concepts such as "project" are meaningless to them, they need practical examples (recipes, wishes).	Questions about homework, posters and school activities are inappropriate and should be removed.	Design questions as simple life scenarios (wishes, bills, recipes). Avoid school contexts; take into account the actual level of digital competence.
Length and repetitiveness of the tool	Too much material, tiring document, feeling of "always the same, just in different colours".	The questionnaire needs a thorough overhaul – in its current form, seniors will only understand a few questions.	Too many questions, duplicates ("identical" items in skills), suggest combining similar questions.	Limit the number of questions, remove duplicates, reduce the number of pages. Rule: short, unambiguous, unique items.
Proposed target length	"One, maximum one double-sided printed sheet".	12–14 basic questions to ensure that the results are reliable and not "sloppy".	Combine similar questions into one, reduce excess.	Goal: a short tool – approx. 1–2 pages, 12–14 well-thought-out items.
Tool structure (logic)	First, general questions about information retrieval, then resistance to manipulation, and finally AI and details.	First, the basics: awareness of what AI is, whether the senior citizen uses AI at all (e.g. ChatGPT/Gemini).	No clear logic – many questions seem practically identical.	Arrange the tool from general to specific : (1) awareness of AI, (2) simple uses, (3) critical thinking/manipulation, (4) more advanced aspects (if any).
Adapt to seniors' experiences	Seniors often use AI (Spotify, YouTube) unconsciously; AI is an abstraction to them because no one explains it to them.	Low digitisation in rural areas – many people have keypad phones, and only a small percentage use smartphones.	It is difficult for seniors to distinguish between subtle categories such as "helpful", "true" and "reliable".	Start from their actual experiences (recommendation streams, search engines, instant messengers), explain AI using examples. Keep technicality to an absolute minimum. Simplify response categories.

Types of examples in questions	Real-life situations for seniors: birthday wishes, short texts for friends – these are understandable examples for them.	Specific tasks: a recipe for chicken soup, wishes for a grandchild, simple everyday activities using AI.	Remove questions about posters, homework, typical school activities.	Construct items based on authentic activities : wishes, recipes, bills, conversations with family, organisation of the day.
Response scale	The scale cannot be long – seniors take too long to consider the nuances ("do I know something very well or a little less").	Limiting the number of questions + simplicity of the scale helps to avoid "get lost" answers.	Too subtle distinctions (helpful/true/useful/reliable) are problematic.	Use a short, simple scale (e.g. 3-point) and avoid labels that are too similar in meaning.
Recognising false content (deepfakes, manipulations)	This indicates that AI is an abstraction – so questions about deepfakes without preparation are too difficult.	Seniors do not understand the concept of "deepfake"; questions about the impact of AI on the world will be assessed intuitively, not based on knowledge. It is important to teach them to distinguish between real/fake recordings.	Has doubts about concepts such as "fair/unfair mistakes" and "treats everyone fairly" – they may be incomprehensible.	Introduce the module on recognising fake content only after building basic awareness of AI; use simple examples (videos, photos).
Form of working with the tool	Indirectly – the tool in its current form is tiring to use individually.	It is estimated that approximately 30% of seniors will need assistance in completing the test; conducting the test in a group of 10 people may take a long time.	With a large number of questions, seniors may become discouraged, even when the response format is simple.	Plan time and support : anticipate the role of an assistant/educator, use the formula "we read together, we mark together", especially in groups with a lower level of digitalisation.

Summary: Recommended Scale Items for sAILS; an AI Literacy Tool for Polish Seniors (Rural Context)

(Based on expert interviews and geragogical/andragogical principles)

Core principles for item construction

The scale (Appendix H) must be:

- Short (12–14 items total)
- Simple (colloquial, non-technical language)
- Concrete (rooted in everyday senior activities)
- Non-abstract (avoid conceptual or policy-level AI questions)
- Visually clear (large font, simple layout)
- Low cognitive load (no duplicates, short scale, one idea per item)
- A 3-point response scale ("Yes / Sometimes / No" or "Can do independently / With help / Cannot do") is recommended.

Domains to include in the scale

The interviews reveal four *necessary* domains for measuring AI literacy in rural older adults.

Domain A: Awareness and basic understanding of AI (3–4 items)

Focus: whether the senior *recognises* AI in everyday tools.

Items should assess:

- Awareness that some apps/services use automatic recommendations.
- Ability to recognise that digital assistants "generate" answers.

- Understanding that some online content may not be real (very basic).

Example item types:

“I know that some apps (e.g., YouTube, Spotify) suggest things automatically.”

“I know that some online messages or videos can be altered or fake.”

Avoid:

Any mention of “deepfake”, “algorithm”, “large language model”, “AI fairness”, etc.

Domain B: Everyday AI-supported tasks (4–5 items)

Experts stressed that items must be practical, everyday, and meaningful to rural seniors.

Items should assess the ability to use AI or digital tools to:

- Write a short message (birthday wishes, greetings).
- Find a recipe (e.g., chicken soup).
- Get simple information (opening hours, weather, directions).
- Compose a shopping list or daily plan.
- Search for information about benefits, health appointments, and village services.

These tasks reflect real usage patterns rather than formal digital skills.

Example item types:

“I can ask a tool to help me write wishes for a family member.”

“I can use my phone to find a simple recipe when I need it.”

“I can ask a tool to remind me of something important.”

Avoid:

Project planning, poster creation, emails with attachments, spreadsheets.

Domain C: Safety & recognising false or harmful content (3–4 items)

Experts repeatedly stressed that seniors struggle with misinformation, especially visual content.

Items should assess:

- Whether the senior can pause before trusting a video or message.
- Whether they know they can ask a family member / educator for help.
- Awareness that online content can be misleading.
- Ability to check if a message looks suspicious.

Example item types:

“When I see a surprising message or video, I check with someone I trust.”

“I know that videos online may not always show real events.”

“I can tell when a message looks suspicious (e.g., too urgent).”

Avoid:

Terms like “fair/unfair mistakes”, “bias”, “AI ethics”, “algorithmic transparency”.

Domain D: Basic digital preconditions (2–3 items)

Because rural seniors often lack devices or regular access, the scale must measure foundational elements.

Items should assess:

- Confidence in using the senior’s own device (phone/tablet).
- Ability to navigate basic functions: opening apps, typing short text.
- Whether they need support to complete tasks.

Example item types:

“I can open an app on my phone by myself.”

“I can type a short message on my device.”

“I sometimes need help to use digital tools.”

Avoid:

Any assumption that they consistently use email, social media, or smartphones.

Items to Explicitly *Remove* or *Avoid*

Experts unanimously warned against these:

A. Overly abstract or technical concepts

AI “fairness”, “unfair mistakes”

“Treats everyone fairly”

“Impact of AI on the world”

“Programming”, “algorithms”, “data sets”

B. School-based examples

Writing homework

Creating posters

Completing school projects

C. Tasks irrelevant to rural seniors

Collaboration tools (“plan a project together”)

Email account creation or management

Multistep digital tasks

D. Long or confusing response scales

Avoid subtle distinctions (helpful / true / useful / reliable).

Avoid 5–7-point Likert scales.

Recommended structure of the final scale

Based on respondents’ insights:

SECTION 1 – General awareness (3 items)

Simple, reality-based statements.

SECTION 2 – Everyday tasks with AI (4–5 items)

Contextualised in seniors’ daily routines.

SECTION 3 – Safety & misinformation (3–4 items)

Basic, practical, example-driven.

SECTION 4 – Device readiness (2–3 items)

Foundational digital competences.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study shows that people do not use artificial intelligence in separate or clearly defined skill categories. In everyday use, different abilities are blended together. When people work with AI, they usually create content, ask questions, adjust their wording, and judge the results at the same time. The analysis found that writing prompts and creating content are closely connected, as are using AI tools and checking whether their outputs are accurate. Many participants also linked creativity with responsibility, for example by thinking about fairness or harm while generating content. Only a smaller group focused mainly on ethical judgment on its own. Overall, AI use works as a combined process rather than a set of isolated skills.

The findings also show that many people have a limited understanding of how AI works. Nearly half of the participants struggled with basic knowledge questions, such as knowing that AI systems can make mistakes or rely on existing data. These differences were not related to age or gender but were strongly connected to educational background. Participants in academic tracks tended to perform better than those in vocational tracks. This suggests that access to clear and reliable information about AI is uneven.

There was also a clear difference between how experts and users understood the assessment questions. Experts generally found the questions clear and appropriate, but many participants found them difficult to relate to their own experiences. Terms that experts considered common, such as “algorithm” or “bias,” were often confusing or unfamiliar. For some users, the questions felt too abstract or too academic, which made it harder for them to answer confidently.

Some groups faced additional difficulties. Technical language and complex sentences created problems for people with lower language proficiency, including refugees. Many examples used in the questions, such as office work or programming, did not match the daily lives of vocational students or older adults, especially those living in rural areas and those inactive in the labour market (e.g. retired). Long questionnaires also caused tiredness and confusion, particularly among older participants.

These findings suggest that AI literacy tools need to better reflect how people actually use AI. Skills that naturally belong together, such as using AI and checking its output, should be assessed together. The focus should be on what people can do while working with AI, rather than on separating skills into strict categories.

The language used in assessments should be simple and familiar. Technical or academic terms should be replaced by everyday words, and questions should include clear examples drawn from daily life, such as looking up information, writing messages, or using social media. Questions should not assume previous knowledge of programming or specialist concepts .

The overall design of assessment tools should also be simpler and shorter. Repeated or similar questions should be reduced, and each question should serve a clear purpose. When there is a difference between expert opinion and user understanding, the way users interpret the questions should guide final decisions.

Finally, accessibility and user-friendliness should be treated as key principles in the development of assessment tools. AI literacy instruments must account for diverse educational backgrounds, language abilities, and life circumstances. For older adults and others facing structural, social, or digital disadvantages, assessments should be concise, easy to read, and, where necessary, supported by an assistant. By prioritising clarity, relevance, and everyday applicability, assessment tools can more accurately capture the actual knowledge and skills of the specific target groups they are designed to evaluate. This understanding is essential for informing the development of educational programmes, tools, and policies that support people in using AI in a confident and responsible manner.

7. Acknowledgements

We would like to warmly thank the institutions that generously opened their doors and made this research possible. In particular, we are deeply grateful to the Fedasil Refugee Centre in Overijse (Belgium) for their openness, trust, and support throughout the research process. Above all, we wish to thank the children and elderly people who participated in this study. Their time, curiosity, and willingness to share their experiences were at the very heart of this research and made it both possible and meaningful.

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9. Appendices

A. Rapid Review study overview

	Scale	Doi/URL
1	AI Literacy Test; 31 items	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2023.100165
2	AI-CI—AI literacy concept inventory assessment ; 20 items	https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-024-00398-x
3	AILQ—AI literacy questionnaire; 32 items	https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13411
4	AILS—AI literacy scale; 12 items	doi.org/10.1111/bjet.13411
5	AI self-efficacy scale (AISES)	doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12015-w
6	EVT Instrument	doi.org/10.1186/s40561-023-00284-4
7	ChatGPT Literacy Scale	https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-024-05723-0
8	GSE-6AI	https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2024.1293437
9	Digital literacy scale in the artificial intelligence era	https://doi.org/10.3837/tiis.2023.08.016
10	Intelligent TPACK	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2022.107468
11	The Artificial Intelligence Literacy Scale for Middle School Students	https://doi.org/10.9708/jksci.2022.27.03.225
12	MAILS	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbah.2023.100014
13	MAIRS-MS	https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-021-02546-6
14	Pinski & Belian’s Instrument	https://hdl.handle.net/10125/102649
15	SAIL4ALL	https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/bvyku
16	SNAIL	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbr.2023.100338
17	UNESCO AI competency framework for students	https://doi.org/10.54675/JKJB9835
18	Empowering Learners for the Age of AI: An AI Literacy Framework for Primary and Secondary Education	https://ailiteracyframework.org

B. Distribution of Correct Responses Across the 30 AI Knowledge Items: Results of the Survey in Belgium

Knowledge					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	.00	6	.5	.5	.5
	1.00	16	1.3	1.4	2.0
	2.00	14	1.1	1.3	3.2
	3.00	11	.9	1.0	4.2
	4.00	22	1.8	2.0	6.2
	5.00	18	1.5	1.6	7.8
	6.00	25	2.0	2.3	10.1
	7.00	27	2.2	2.4	12.5
	8.00	36	2.9	3.2	15.8
	9.00	26	2.1	2.3	18.1
	10.00	23	1.9	2.1	20.2
	11.00	36	2.9	3.2	23.4
	12.00	62	5.0	5.6	29.0
	13.00	44	3.6	4.0	33.0
	14.00	49	4.0	4.4	37.4
	15.00	52	4.2	4.7	42.1
	16.00	71	5.8	6.4	48.5
	17.00	53	4.3	4.8	53.2
	18.00	87	7.1	7.8	61.1
	19.00	60	4.9	5.4	66.5
	20.00	70	5.7	6.3	72.8
	21.00	90	7.3	8.1	80.9
	22.00	70	5.7	6.3	87.2
	23.00	55	4.5	5.0	92.2
	24.00	44	3.6	4.0	96.1
	25.00	25	2.0	2.3	98.4
	26.00	12	1.0	1.1	99.5
	27.00	6	.5	.5	100.0
	Total	1110	90.4	100.0	
Missing	System	118	9.6		
Total		1228	100.0		

C. Full overview of Initial AI Literacy Scale

AI Skill Items

Dimension	AI Skill Item
Technical and operational	1. I know how to use an AI-based tool (e.g. a voice assistant or ChatGPT) to complete a specific task or activity.
	2. I know how to write clear and effective prompts or questions to get useful results from a generative AI tool (e.g. ChatGPT, DALL,E).
	3. I know how to improve the answers I get from an AI tool by changing or refining my prompts or questions.
	4. I know how to choose the most suitable AI tool or app for what I want to do.
	5. I know how to check and adjust the privacy or security settings when using an AI tool (e.g. disabling data sharing or deleting chat histories)
	6. I know how to use AI tools to make my work or study tasks more efficient.
Information navigation and processing	7. I know how to find and select reliable information or content with the help of AI tools.
	8. I know how to check whether information created or suggested by AI is true and trustworthy.
	9. I know how to recognize when AI-generated content is incomplete, misleading, or biased.
	10. I know how to verify AI-generated information by evaluating its accuracy and checking it against credible sources.
	11. I know how to integrate information from AI tools with insights from other sources to form a comprehensive understanding.
	12. I know how to distinguish when to accept, revise, or reject AI-generated content based on its quality
Content creation and production	13. I know how to do creative writing or storytelling using an AI tool (e.g., ChatGPT or Gemini).
	14. I know how to design and develop projects or applications that use AI tools.
	15. I know how to select useful tools (e.g., frameworks, programming languages) to program an AI.
	16. I know how to use AI in assignments while respecting rules on originality and plagiarism.
	17. I know how to use AI to create a poster for an event I am organizing.
	18. I know how to use AI (e.g., Gemini or ChatGPT) to make a social media post gain more attention
Communication and interaction	19. I know how to ask clear and specific questions when I use an AI chatbot (e.g. ChatGPT, DALL-E) so I get helpful answers.
	20. I know how to recognize when an AI tool gives a wrong or confusing answer and ask it again in a clearer way.
	21. I know how to work with an AI tool to plan or create something together, such as a story, design, or project.
	22. I know how to use AI tools to help me write or reply to messages, posts, or emails when communicating with other people.
	23. I know how to recognize when AI tools don't think or feel like people when I talk or write to them.
	24. I know how to use and talk with different kinds of AI systems (e.g. ChatGPT or Google Assistant)
Ethical and responsible use	25. I know how to test an AI app (like an image-recognition tool) by giving it different examples to see if it makes fair or unfair response.
	26. I know how to compare how an AI tool works for different kinds of people to check if it treats everyone fairly.
	27. I know how to double-check answers from an AI tool (e.g. ChatGPT) using trusted sources to see if they are correct and safe to use.
	28. I know how avoid sharing personal details when using an AI tool to keep my information safe.
	29. I know how to find real examples of how AI has changed people's jobs, environment, education, or daily life.
	30. I know how to distinguish who should take responsibility when an AI system causes a problem and explain my reasons.

AI Knowledge Items

Dimension	AI Knowledge Item
Technical and operational	1. AI systems follow rules made by people and a combination of math and logic to make choices.
	2. AI systems get better by practicing with lots of data and learning from their mistakes.
	3. Tools like ChatGPT make new things by finding patterns in data, but they don't really understand what they say.
	4. AI can think and make its own choices without help from people.
	5. AI always works perfectly, and it cannot make mistakes.
	6. Once an AI is made, people can't change or fix it anymore.
Information navigation and processing	7. The answers given by AI tools are always correct, so there is no need to double-check them.
	8. Different people can get different results from AI tools even when they ask the same question.
	9. AI-generated content can sometimes mix true and false information.
	10. It does not matter how you phrase your question, as AI tools will always give the same quality of answer.
	11. AI tools are completely free from human bias.
	12. Everything shown or suggested by AI tools online can be trusted as neutral and reliable.
Content creation and production	13. Companies can use AI to create ads based on the data I share online.
	14. When using AI, the tools and content should be adapted to the specific context and audience (e.g., creating something for children versus for adults).
	15. Multimodal prompting means giving an AI both words and images to help understand a question.
	16. AI can create completely original content, without using existing information.
	17. Using AI tools to do homework or assignments is the same as doing it myself
	18. Using AI to make content has nothing to do with fairness, credit, or using other people's work responsibly.
Communication and interaction	19. An AI system can be asked to give answers as if it were talking to a different kind of person (for example, someone younger or with different opinions).
	20. AI tools can influence the opinions I see online.
	21. An AI app may respond unpleasantly to my prompts.
	22. I should talk to AI tools as if it were a person, being polite, so I don't have problems.
	23. If I create a "Deepfake" of someone just for fun, it cannot hurt them.
	24. There is no risk in getting emotional support from an AI.
Ethical and responsible use	25. AI systems can sometimes create harmful or inappropriate content.
	26. Human workers help build, train, and look after AI tools.
	27. AI should be made and used in ways that are fair, clear, and safe for everyone.
	28. AI tools always make fair and correct decisions without mistakes.
	29. AI tools never cause any social or environmental problems.
	30. Training and running AI systems does not use much energy or harm the environment.

D. yAILS Refined Scale

Below, you can find the reformulated AI Skills and Knowledge items, for measuring AI literacy among vulnerable youth (yAILS) and seniors (sAILS). The items in this scales are updated based on results from the pilot survey, feedback from experts, and interviews with participants in all countries. For each question, we looked at *how well it worked* in the survey across Belgian Schools, *how people understood it* during the cognitive interviews, *how experts rated the questions* and *how strongly it related to the skill or knowledge* it was meant to measure.

Most changes were made to make the questions more straightforward to understand and more relevant to everyday use of AI. Technical or unclear terms were replaced with simple language and familiar examples. Examples of these changes can be found in table 5.

Table 2: Rewording in Final Scale

<i>Original wording</i>	<i>Revised wording</i>
Privacy or security settings	Turn off data sharing
Deleting chat histories	Delete my chat
Fair or unfair responses	Does not treat anyone badly
Responsibility and accountability	Who is to blame, and why
Societal impact	Real examples from daily life
Environmental impact	Using lots of water or electricity

Some questions that covered very similar ideas were combined, while others that required advanced technical knowledge were removed. We also adjusted how the questions were grouped to better reflect how people actually use AI, for example, when creating content or communicating with others.

Table 3: Unclear Distinctions

<i>Removed distinction</i>	<i>How it was handled</i>
Task vs. activity	Combined into one idea
Tool vs. app	Used “AI” or “AI app” consistently
Prompt vs. question	Used “question” only

In addition, examples were added to clarify what is meant by AI tools or apps such as Siri or ChatGPT, and questions about responsible use were rewritten to focus on real-world impacts, such as privacy, fairness, and environmental effects. Overall, these changes were made to ensure that the questions are clear, meaningful, and suitable for our three participant groups.

Refinement of Youth AI Literacy Scale (Skill Items)

Dimension	Original item	Final Scale Item	Changes made
Technical and operational	I know how to use an AI-based tool (e.g., a voice assistant or ChatGPT) to complete a specific task or activity.	1. <i>I know how to use AI (for example, Siri or Chat GPT) to do my homework</i>	<i>From general “AI-based tool for any task” to concrete school-related use (“do my homework”); simpler wording</i>
	I know how to write clear and effective prompts or questions to get useful results from a generative AI tool (e.g. ChatGPT, DALL.E).	2. <i>I know how to ask clear questions to AI (e.g. Chat GPT) to get helpful answers</i>	<i>Write clear and effective prompts” → “ask clear questions”; removes technical term prompt.</i>
	I know how to improve the answers I get from an AI tool by changing or refining my prompts or questions.	3. <i>I know how to change my questions to make AI give me a better answer</i>	<i>Keeps same skill but expressed in everyday language (“change my questions”).</i>
	I know how to choose the most suitable AI tool or app for what I want to do.	4. <i>I know how to pick the best AI app (e.g. DALL.E or Snapchat AI) for what I want to do.</i>	<i>“Choose the most suitable AI tool” → “pick the best AI app”; adds familiar apps (Snapchat AI).</i>
	I know how to check and adjust the privacy or security settings when using an AI tool (e.g. disabling data sharing or deleting chat histories).	5. <i>I know how to turn off data sharing when using AI</i>	<i>From multiple privacy actions (check/adjust settings) to one concrete action (turn off data sharing).</i>
		6. <i>I know how to delete my chat with AI.</i>	<i>Original focus on efficiency → revised focus on a specific operational action (delete chat).</i>
Information navigation and processing	I know how to find and select reliable information or content with the help of AI tools.	7. <i>I know how to find and select information I can trust with the help of AI</i>	<i>Reliable information” → “information I can trust”; maintains meaning with simpler phrasing.</i>
	I know how to check whether information created or suggested by AI is true and trustworthy.	8. <i>I know how to check if the information from AI is correct</i>	<i>Removes abstract phrasing (“true and trustworthy”), focuses on correctness.</i>

	I know how to recognize when AI-generated content is incomplete, misleading, or biased.	9. <i>I know how to explain the difference between searching with AI and searching with a search engine like Google</i>	<i>“Incomplete, misleading, or biased” → “incomplete, confusing or one-sided.”</i>
	I know how to verify AI-generated information by evaluating its accuracy and checking it against credible sources.	10. <i>I know how to check if AI’s answers are correct by comparing them with trusted sources.</i>	<i>Keeps same verification skill; simpler, more direct phrasing.</i>
	I know how to integrate information from AI tools with insights from other sources to form a comprehensive understanding.	11. <i>I can put AI answers and other sources together to help me understand something completely.</i>	<i>“Integrate information” → “put together”; meaning unchanged.</i>
	I know how to distinguish when to accept, revise, or reject AI-generated content based on its quality.	12. <i>I know how to check when an AI answer is good, needs fixing, or should not be used.</i>	<i>“Accept, revise, or reject” → “good, needs fixing, or should not be used.”</i>
Content creation and production + Communication & Interaction	I know how to do creative writing or storytelling using an AI tool (e.g., ChatGPT or Gemini).	13. <i>I know how to make different kinds of creations (like stories, music, drawings or ideas) using AI</i>	<i>From writing/storytelling to multiple creative formats (music, drawings, ideas).</i>
	I know how to use AI in assignments while respecting rules on originality and plagiarism.	14. <i>I know how to use AI for schoolwork without copying other people’s work</i>	<i>Original technical project/app development removed; replaced by plagiarism-aware school use.</i>
	I know how to use AI (e.g., Gemini or ChatGPT) to make a social media post gain more attention.	15. <i>I know how to use AI to make a social media post get more likes or views.</i>	<i>New emphasis on social media performance; not present in original programming-focused items.</i>
	I know how to work with an AI tool to plan	16. <i>I know how to communicate with AI and work together with it to</i>	<i>Combines collaboration, communication, and co-creation into one simplified statement.</i>

	or create something together, such as a story, design, or project.	<i>create something (like a story, design or a project)</i>	
	I know how to use AI tools to help me write or reply to messages, posts, or emails when communicating with other people.	17. <i>I know how to use AI to help me write or answer messages, posts or emails when communicating with others.</i>	<i>Minor wording changes; maintains same communication support skill</i>
	I know how to recognize when AI tools don't think or feel like people when I talk or write to them.	18. <i>I know how to notice that AI doesn't think or feel like a real person when I talk or write to it.</i>	<i>Simplifies recognition that AI does not think or feel like humans.</i>
<i>Ethical and responsible use</i>	I know how to test an AI app (like an image-recognition tool) by giving it different examples to see if it makes fair or unfair response.	19. <i>I know how to try out an AI app with different examples to check if it does not treat anyone badly.</i>	<i>"Fair/unfair responses" → "does not treat anyone badly."</i>
	I know how to find real examples of how AI has changed people's jobs, environment, education, or daily life.	20. <i>I know how to find real examples of how AI can affect the planet, like using lots of water or electricity.</i>	<i>Replaces fairness comparison with environmental impact examples (water, electricity).</i>
	I know how to double-check answers from an AI tool (e.g. ChatGPT) using trusted sources to see if they are correct and safe to use.	21. <i>I know how to explain how AI changes daily easier but also how it can cause harm if used the wrong way</i>	<i>Combines benefits and harms into one accessible explanatory skill.</i>
	I know how avoid sharing personal details when using an AI tool to keep my information safe.	22. <i>When using AI, I know how to avoid sharing personal information like my name or address to keep me safe.</i>	<i>"Avoid sharing personal details" → concrete examples (name, address) and personal safety focus.</i>
	I know how to find real examples of	23. <i>I know how to find real examples of how AI has</i>	<i>From broad societal impacts to specific job loss examples.</i>

	<p>how AI has changed people's jobs, environment, education, or daily life.</p>	<p><i>made some people lose their jobs.</i></p>	
	<p>I know how to distinguish who should take responsibility when an AI system causes a problem and explain my reasons.</p>	<p>24. <i>I know how to decide who is to blame when AI causes a problem, and say why.</i></p>	<p><i>"Distinguish responsibility" → "decide who is to blame and say why."</i></p>

Refinement of Youth AI Literacy Scale (Knowledge Items)

Dimension	Original item	Final Scale Item	Changes made
Technical and operational	1. <i>AI systems get better by practicing with lots of data and learning from their mistakes.</i>		<i>No change; item retained verbatim</i>
	2. <i>AI always works perfectly, and it cannot make mistakes.</i>		<i>No change; item retained verbatim</i>
Information navigation and processing	The answers given by AI are always correct, so there is no need to check again.	3. <i>The answers given by AI are always correct, so there is no need to check again.</i>	<i>Minor wording simplification (“tools” removed; “double-check” → “check again”).</i>
	Different people can get different results from AI tools even when they ask the same question.	4. <i>Different people can get different results from AI even when they ask the same question.</i>	<i>Minor wording simplification (“tools” removed).</i>
	5. <i>AI-generated content can sometimes mix true and false information.</i>		<i>No change; item retained verbatim.</i>
Content creation and production; Communication and interaction	Using AI tools to do homework or assignments is the same as doing it myself	6. <i>Copy and pasting AI answers feels the same as solving my homework myself.</i>	<i>Reworded to be more concrete and behaviour-specific (“using AI tools” → “copy and pasting AI answers”); meaning preserved.</i>
	I should talk to AI tools as if it were a person, being polite, so I don’t have problems.	7. <i>I should talk to AI politely, like to a person, so I don’t get into trouble.</i>	<i>Minor wording simplification; meaning unchanged.</i>
Ethical and responsible use	Training and running AI systems does not use much energy or harm the environment.	8. <i>AI doesn’t use a lot of energy and is not bad for the planet.</i>	<i>Simplified language; abstract phrasing replaced with everyday wording.</i>
	9. <i>I think it is safe to get emotional support from AI.</i>		<i>No change; item retained verbatim.</i>
	AI systems can sometimes create harmful or inappropriate content	10. <i>AI systems can create harmful or inappropriate content.</i>	<i>Minor wording change (“sometimes” removed); meaning retained.</i>

E. Initial sAILS

(still needs to be validated)

PRODIGI PRE-TEST

1. Please provide the last three digits of your telephone number:
2. Please enter your year of birth: _____
3. How would you describe your gender? Male Female Other
4. What is the highest level of education you have completed?
 Primary school or less Secondary school, including technical school Vocational school
 Bachelor's degree Master's degree or PhD Other (please specify):
5. What is your current situation? I am working I am not working I am retired or receiving a pension

For each statement, please select one answer: **True** – if the statement is true; **False** – if the statement is false; **I don't know** – if you are unsure. Mark your answer by placing an X in the selected column. There are no wrong answers – the test helps to identify which topics should be discussed in class.

No	Question	True	False	I don't know
1	I can add a photo or document as an attachment to an e-mail.			
2	A web search engine can find information in the form of text, recordings and videos.			
3	Clicking on a link in an e-mail is always safe if it comes from a company I know.			
4	I will get more accurate search results if I enter more specific keywords.			
5	Fake news often has sensational headlines to attract attention.			
6	Any photo found on the internet can be edited to look real.			
7	If a post is shared frequently, it means it is true.			
8	To check the credibility of information, it is worth comparing it across several sources (e.g. on different websites).			
9	Artificial intelligence can write any text for me, e.g. a letter to a loved one or a message in response to my letter.			
10	AI can help find information in every area of life.			
11	Texts generated by AI may contain factual errors.			
12	Sometimes you can recognise AI-generated content by unusual errors.			
13	AI can create realistic images or recordings of different people to make them look authentic.			
14	We can provide AI with personal data, and it will certainly not share it with anyone – these systems are currently very secure.			
15	Accessing and using artificial intelligence (e.g. ChatGPT) requires significant financial resources.			

Please select one answer in each column that best describes your feelings. There are no wrong answers – please answer according to your own beliefs.

No	Question	Strongly NO	Rather NO	Sometimes yes, sometimes no	Rather YES	Definitely YES
1	I use a phone, computer or tablet for everyday tasks.					
2	I feel comfortable using the basic functions of digital devices (text messages, e-mail, the internet).					
3	I have previously used applications that assist with tasks (maps, translators, hints).					
4	I find it easy to learn how to use new devices or applications when someone shows me step by step.					
5	I believe that AI tools do not have to be difficult to use.					
6	I would be able to use AI with calm instruction.					
7	I find the instructions for AI understandable.					
8	I feel that I can learn to use AI at my own pace.					
9	I believe AI can help me with my daily tasks.					
10	AI could make it easier for me to search for information.					
11	I believe that AI can save me time or effort.					
12	I can see situations where AI could be really helpful to me.					
13	I feel that using AI can be safe.					
14	I am concerned that AI could use my data without my consent. (reversed)					
15	I trust that AI will not do anything I do not instruct it to do.					
16	I feel more confident about AI when I understand how it works.					
17	I would like to try AI-based tools.					
18	I am ready to learn how to use AI step by step.					
19	If I had the opportunity, I would use AI in my daily tasks.					
20	I believe that using AI could be valuable for me.					